

DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM FOR THE NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS

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D4.2 - Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – intermediate version

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DMS	Document Management System
DTPC	Deputy Technical Project Coordinator
EAG	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FACL	Financial & Administrative Coordinator Leader
GA	Grant Agreement
KOM	Kick-off meeting
LCMS	Learning Content Management System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
R&I	Research and Innovation
SG	Stakeholder Group
The Consortium	All the Project Partners: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TL	Task Leader
TWG	Thematic Working Group
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Community, Engagement, Stakeholders, Collaboration, Inclusivity, Communication, Outreach, Participation

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

The DigiNEB project supports the implementation of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) and the acceleration of the green transformation by increasing the adoption of NEB-aligned digital solutions. As a Coordination Action, DigiNEB has prioritised the identification and understanding of stakeholder needs to provide targeted knowledge support, networking opportunities, upskilling, and community participation. This document outlines the updated engagement objectives, evolving stakeholder groups, engagement channels, risks, and the roles and responsibilities of DigiNEB's partners.

The DigiNEB platform aims to deepen stakeholder understanding of the New European Bauhaus, keep stakeholders informed of key developments, contribute to the NEB digital transformation, and disseminate NEB best practices. It also fosters cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration, monitors the overall impact of NEB activities, and contributes to policy development and standardisation.

In 2023, DigiNEB played a pivotal role in rallying the NEB community around the NEB Mission, engaging Member States to support it during a key meeting at the Council of Europe on the 12th of September 2023. Following this, DigiNEB gathered eminent leaders from NEB Labs and Lighthouses to co-author a White Paper. This document, which is included as an annex to this report, provides strategic direction for the NEB Mission's evolution and its eventual transition towards the NEB Facility, a future-focused funding mechanism. The White Paper captures the insights of thought leaders from across the NEB ecosystem and serves as a foundational guide for shaping the NEB's future, policy, and initiatives.

This updated Stakeholder Engagement Plan moves beyond addressing the initial catalogue of distinct target groups - architects, designers, educators, etc. Based on insights from the project's first phase and in consultation with partners, the plan has adopted a more flexible, mission-driven approach. This strategy unites multidisciplinary communities around topics of shared interest, following successful models from NEB projects such as *Bauhaus of the Seas Sails*, *Nordic Carbon-Neutral Bauhaus* and *Bauhaus Goes South*. Aligning DigiNEB with these core themes has proven effective for onboarding large stakeholder pools, encouraging cross-sectoral collaboration, and promoting co-creation.

One key evolution is the shift in how DigiNEB engages with its digital tools and community resources. A major upgrade to the DigiNEB website provides a more intuitive and user-friendly interface, enhancing stakeholder access to valuable resources such as the *Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation* and the new *NEB Concepts* podcast. The revamped website now functions as a central hub for stakeholders, offering improved navigation, interactive learning tools, and databases that support co-creation activities.

The DigiNEB project is actively connecting with industry partners, European Digital Innovation Hubs (including Linköping Science Park), the EU Capital of Innovation (Linköping, Sweden), and a range of digital projects in alignment with the objectives set out in the Description of Action (DOA). Through the digital technical working groups/digital focus groups, a broad spectrum of stakeholders from different EU member and associated states has been engaged.

The *NEB Concepts* podcast, a new addition to the project's outreach tools, was created as a response to challenges in sustaining meaningful engagement through traditional social media. It offers a modular approach, allowing users to explore themes such as sustainability, design, and innovation in a flexible format that promotes deeper learning and engagement. This podcast represents a shift

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toward more substantive, long-term engagement strategies, moving away from the transient nature of social media.

The *Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation* further supports DigiNEB's mission by offering local and regional leaders practical guidance on how to implement NEB principles within their own contexts. By focusing on ecosystemic approaches to regional development, the handbook ensures that the NEB community can benefit from proven methodologies and tools that drive innovation and collaboration across Europe.

In addition to these resources, the project has undergone significant development, including the redesign of the **DigiNEB website** to provide a more intuitive and accessible hub for stakeholders. This upgraded platform offers enhanced features such as interactive learning tools, improved navigation, and the integration of **digital co-creation methodologies**.

DigiNEB established a repository after the NEB@CERN event, providing an ongoing resource for the NEB community. This platform, initially created to support collaboration following the event, has led to ongoing interaction by that community of contributors, hosted by sister projects such as CrAft and the NEB Academy. The community unified by this milestone event at CERN has maintained regular dialogue, collaboration and interaction, driving forward the collective NEB vision.

Stakeholder engagement has evolved significantly, with new strategies focusing on collaboration, community participation, and co-creation. Key NEB stakeholders, including policymakers, industry leaders, and civil society, have been actively involved in the development of best practices for regional innovation. The project's engagement strategy now emphasises **data ethics and AI for social good**, integrating these themes into broader discussions around sustainability and digital transformation. These efforts are aligned with the project's goal of fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and supporting the NEB mission at the European level.

Stakeholder engagement remains a shared responsibility of all DigiNEB consortium members. Leveraging existing networks and connections remains a core aspect of the project's outreach strategy. Each partner continues to focus on specific areas of engagement, ensuring that the project benefits from a diverse range of strengths and avoids duplication of efforts. Stakeholder engagement has also been conducted in parallel lines of community interaction, by participation in broad interest community activities of DigiNEB project partners. This collaborative approach, paired with the updated tools and methodologies outlined in this document, positions DigiNEB to foster interdisciplinary collaboration and advance the NEB's mission effectively.

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1. Introduction

The predecessor to this document, *D4.1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption & Monitoring Report – Initial Version*, outlined the strategy for engaging stakeholders in the New European Bauhaus (NEB) digital ecosystem. The core aim of the document was to create a collaborative platform where stakeholders from diverse backgrounds could interact, co-create, and enhance the adoption of NEB digital solutions. The engagement strategy focused on fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration, upskilling, and increasing capacity across stakeholder groups. The deliverable emphasised the importance of trust-building, community engagement, and a two-way dialogue to ensure that the platform and its tools met the evolving needs of its users.

The document identified several key objectives:

1. **Community Onboarding and Collaboration:** The engagement plan stressed the need to connect stakeholders from both the digital and NEB communities, ensuring that different groups worked together towards common goals. The onboarding process included the creation of Thematic Working Groups (TWGs), reframed from their original Technology Working Groups, to facilitate collaboration based on shared themes rather than siloed expertise.
2. **Engagement Channels:** Several methods were identified to reach stakeholders, including the DigiNEB website, eLearning platforms, webinars, workshops, and the NEB Digital Toolkit. The project also leveraged existing NEB networks, such as the NEB Lab and Lighthouse projects, to ensure broad and effective outreach.
3. **Stakeholder Diversity:** Engagement went beyond typical groups like architects or educators and aimed to bring together a wide spectrum of disciplines, from digital innovators to policymakers, to collaborate on sustainable, inclusive digital solutions.
4. **Monitoring and KPIs:** The document established mechanisms for impact measurement, including monitoring adoption rates of digital tools and setting up dashboards for continuous feedback. This ongoing monitoring helped to refine strategies and adjust stakeholder engagement activities.

Deliverable 4.1 aligned with the tasks outlined in Work Package 4 (WP4), specifically **Task 4.1: Stakeholder Engagement**. The DoA had specified the need to create a framework for engaging NEB and digital stakeholders and identifying synergies between the two communities. *D4.1's* emphasis on building trust and promoting two-way communication directly supported the DoA's objective of enhancing the uptake of NEB digital tools and encouraging collaboration. Additionally, the structure and timeline for engagement helped track progress towards the broader goals of the DigiNEB project as outlined in the DoA.

Key successes, such as the early execution of the CERN event, delivered substantial stakeholder engagement well ahead of schedule. However, the need to revise elements of the communication and online dissemination strategy necessitated a more comprehensive review of the original plan outlined in *D4.1*. The result was a shift in the project's focus and timeline, with some objectives being achieved ahead of expectations and others requiring recalibration.

This led to a significant project amendment, a reset of the engagement strategy and, consequently, adjustments to the project timeline. The DigiNEB consortium conducted a thorough review of the stakeholder engagement plan and the execution of several key aspects related to the online platform's communication and dissemination activities. While significant progress was made, it became clear that several areas required adjustments.

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The revised plan addresses the lessons learned from the early success stories and lessons learned from in-person engagement with the broader community of champions and early adopters. Communication improvements have focused on the redevelopment and complete redesign of the DigiNEB website, the introduction of new engagement channels, and a renewed focus on data ethics and AI for social good as a central pillar of engagement activities. These refinements were driven by the desire to build a more sustainable, impactful, and long-term engagement strategy that could better serve the evolving needs of the NEB community.

This intermediate deliverable, *D4.2*, expands upon the work initiated in *D4.1*. It focuses on progress, identifying objectives, and outlining how the plan has been updated in light of new insights and priorities. In particular, this document will address:

- The outcomes and learnings following the CERN event;
- The objectives reached and the adjustments made to the stakeholder engagement strategy;
- The rationale behind the redesign of the DigiNEB website to enhance community engagement;
- The ongoing evolution of stakeholder engagement channels, including preparations for a ‘DigiNEB day’ focused on *JUST Living Environments: AI for Social Good*, part of the JUST Industry Data Week at Linköping Science Park;
- The integration of new resources, such as the creation of a podcast series and the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation, both of which have their launch during the DigiNEB day at the JUST Industry Data Week in Linköping;

The restructuring of the engagement plan is covered in detail in this document, including updated timelines for *Phase 1* (M1-14) and *Phase 2* (M15-27), new KPIs, and the expanded role of data ethics and AI as a focal point for the remainder of the project. Building on the successes of earlier activities, this deliverable sets the stage for the continued evolution of DigiNEB’s engagement strategy as we move towards the final reporting phase in *D4.3*, which will include key learnings from the JUST Industry Data Week event in Linköping and a concluding project event.

This intermediate version focuses on tracking key engagement milestones, further developing thematic collaborations, and adjusting KPIs as necessary to ensure optimal community involvement. Moving forward to the final Deliverable 4.3, the task will be to report on the resulting methodologies for refining the engagement approach based on interim monitoring results and further intensive interactions with stakeholders.

2. Engagement Objectives

Widespread use of the DigiNEB platform and toolkit is part of the goal of stakeholder engagement. The ethos of the New European Bauhaus requires that stakeholders become more than an atomised cloud of individual users but rather active community participants, bridging digital and technological divides. This participation requires building trust within a diverse group of potential users and stakeholders, and engagement must occur transversally. Trust must be built between silos and among stakeholders from diverse knowledge domains and backgrounds – not simply between each user and the platform but amongst the many kinds of users. Key to this level of engagement is a platform that allows for two-way communication, with dialogue and co-creation as central to the action, rather than one-way dissemination. Initiating the dialogue involves reaching out to NEB partners and engaging with projects, becoming well-informed of existing activities and projects, transforming digital business

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models using NEB principles, connecting across domains and fostering interdisciplinary understanding, and monitoring the evolution of NEB in the global context.

These original engagement objectives, as outlined in *D4.1*, remain crucial to the ongoing efforts of DigiNEB. They were designed to foster collaboration between stakeholders in the NEB and digital communities and facilitate the adoption of NEB principles in alignment with the Green Deal. The following sections outline our original objectives, with updates based on progress to date and emerging priorities.

One of the main goals of DigiNEB is to interlink and unite the NEB community by providing specific mechanisms to identify, segment, and reach out to complementary stakeholder groups. To that end, DigiNEB has elaborated a comprehensive Engagement Strategy for the project, focusing on tackling Engagement Objectives, Target Stakeholder Groups, Engagement Channels, Risks and Mitigations, and the DigiNEB Partners' Engagement Roles and Responsibilities. In doing so, assumptions about the needs and use cases of stakeholders, as well as about the nature and potential of the project, were tested, and accordingly, the ambition and focus of the DigiNEB project's stakeholder engagement were expanded, as demonstrated below.

2.1. Increase understanding between the New European Bauhaus and Smart Communities

The DigiNEB initiative seeks to create a platform for two-way communication, with dialogue and co-creation central to the process. Of primary importance is clarifying what the New European Bauhaus is and what it represents to current and potential future stakeholders.

Understanding how NEB creates meaning for stakeholders involves reaching out to all NEB partners and engaging with existing and developing projects active in the New European Bauhaus ecosystem. Connection with NEB Lab projects and **NEB lighthouse projects** (see 6.1) provides the DigiNEB Coordination Action with an already extensive network of engaged and active stakeholders. Second, attention to innovative tools devised in both the public and private sectors at the European level is essential to enhance the project's outreach and its platform, provided that these innovations are aligned with NEB's three main principles of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics.

While significant progress has been made in this area, particularly through the success of the CERN event, which exceeded several of our KPIs ahead of schedule, the project has identified areas for improvement in digital engagement. Our initial approach to social media and the DigiNEB website did not foster the level of community interaction we aimed for. As a result, we undertook a comprehensive redesign of the DigiNEB website to create a more engaging and user-friendly experience. This revamp is part of a larger strategy to foster ongoing dialogue and improve user retention across all stakeholder groups.

2.2. Increase capacity for all involved stakeholders and support continuous learning

A key objective of the stakeholder engagement strategy is to become and remain constantly well-informed of existing NEB activities and projects on the ground that may have an impact on or are of direct relevance to digital platform creators. In their capacity as Early Adopters, successful NEB community projects have been actively involved in DigiNEB co-creation activities with digital communities for capacity building and contributions to effective Green Deal solutions. The DigiNEB programme includes a variety of methods for capacity building, including multiple webinars, co-creation events, and contribution to the founding of the new NEB Academy (see 2.5). This ensures that all stakeholders have access to the knowledge and skills needed to fully participate in the NEB digital ecosystem.

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Capacity building is the primary focus of the modular *NEB Concepts* podcast series that draws on the knowledge of the NEB champions and thought leaders. The podcast modules allow for the expert knowledge to be searched using tag words for individual topics covered within the areas of sustainability, design, and innovation. This modular podcast allows users to explore a wide range of themes, such as climate adaptation, technology integration, and interdisciplinary collaboration, through insightful conversations with leading architects, educators, and project leaders. By allowing listeners to choose their own pathway and follow either the broader themes or the detailed thoughts of individual interviewees, the podcast offers a flexible, dynamic resource for ongoing learning.

The podcast complements the project’s wider aim of providing content that extends beyond social media platforms, offering a more sustainable and direct form of engagement. With a focus on topics central to the NEB, such as sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design, the podcast highlights practical applications of NEB principles in areas like urban development, cultural heritage, and community empowerment. This positions it as a critical tool for disseminating knowledge and best practices across the NEB community and beyond, allowing stakeholders to access a diverse array of ideas and methodologies that are directly relevant to their work.

The focus on capacity building has evolved with the *Handbook for Regional Ecosystemic Innovation* as a key resource for local administrators and policymakers. Drawing on best practices from JRC and DG REGIO publications and initiatives, as well as insights from NEB Labs and Lighthouse projects, the handbook aims to provide region-specific guidance, activities and management approaches for implementing NEB principles. This resource is being launched during the DigiNEB Day ‘*JUST Living Environments: AI for Social Good*’ at the JUST Industry Data Week at the European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH), Linköping Science Park, with participation both in person and online, further expanding the capacity of stakeholders to contribute to the NEB mission.

This handbook, aimed at local and regional policymakers, civic leaders, and innovators, provides a comprehensive framework for addressing complex societal challenges through ecosystemic thinking. The Handbook advocates for collaborative, interdisciplinary approaches that integrate community engagement and evidence-based policymaking, thereby ensuring that regional innovation efforts are sustainable, inclusive, and adaptive to local needs. It is structured in three parts:

1. **Understanding Ecosystemic Regional Innovation**, which establishes the theoretical foundations for this approach;
2. **Facilitating Ecosystemic Regional Innovation**, which offers practical tools for co-creation and participatory design within communities; and
3. **Managing Ecosystemic Regional Innovation**, which provides strategic guidance for the long-term sustainability and scalability of regional innovation efforts.

By promoting hands-on experimentation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and citizen engagement, the handbook provides local and regional administrators with actionable tools to implement NEB principles in real-world contexts. This resource not only supports continuous community learning but also enables regions to develop resilient, future-facing ecosystems that align with the goals of the New European Bauhaus.

3.1. Contribute to the digital transformation from multiple perspectives

DigiNEB aims to continuously support both New European Bauhaus and Smart Communities breakthroughs, novel projects and initiatives to allow for all engaged stakeholders to keep learning from each other. These include learning through digital and NEB partnerships with global communities.

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As the engagement strategy is not merely one of dissemination but also of providing tools and benefits for users, close collaboration between NEB and digital stakeholders is essential. Co-creation activities have addressed the challenges of digitalisation, with Early Adopter NEB communities contributing insights from sustainability, usability, and accessibility perspectives. DigiNEB leverages the best practices and knowledge from the NEB community to create opportunities for multidisciplinary collaboration towards a triple transformation in Europe: digital, green, and socially inclusive.

Members of the DigiNEB Advisory Board have been notably very active at supporting this objective with significant contributions of knowledge and perspectives to the project. A member from outside the EU has actively supported the global community perspective: Sheela Patel is member of the High Level Round Table of the New European Bauhaus and the founder director of the Society for Promotion of Area Resource Centres (SPARC). She defines herself as an academic and activist who works "with people living in slums and informal settlements in the Global South." Much of her work focuses on education, and she has been a valuable contributor to the project by transferring lessons learned globally.

The success of the CERN event has provided valuable momentum in this area, bringing together NEB stakeholders and digital practitioners in a highly productive environment that surpassed initial expectations. Moving forward, the focus was on ensuring that the outcomes of these collaborations are effectively integrated and multiplied into our digital tools, resources and platforms. The redesigned DigiNEB website and the new podcast series aim to further these interactions and ensure that the co-created solutions have a lasting impact on the broader NEB digital ecosystem.

3.2. Enable cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration

DigiNEB aims to connect across domains and foster interdisciplinary understanding and collaboration. One of the central goals of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) is to blend sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics in ways that transform living environments across Europe. Cross-domain engagement is essential for aligning different sectors—such as technology, urban planning, health, and the arts—around these goals. This creates opportunities for stakeholders to co-create innovative solutions that respond to the complex challenges posed by modern living environments.

The NEB's emphasis on reimagining living spaces as more sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful requires input from a diverse array of disciplines, particularly those where digital tools intersect with physical environments. DigiNEB facilitates this by enabling stakeholders to collaborate across sectors and share best practices that lead to impactful, long-lasting improvements to how we design, build, and experience our environments.

JUST Industry Data Week, taking place at Linköping Science Park in September 2024, is a key event where cross-domain collaboration is put into action to further these NEB goals. This week-long series of discussions, experiments, and workshops focuses on bringing together experts from different industries—health, urban planning, AI, and data sciences—to jointly explore how judicious, unbiased, safe and transparent data practices can be used in AI applications and enhance living environments.

A core component of JUST Industry Data Week is the *Sound for Urban Environments* track, which explores how AI, automation, and data can be used to create healthier, more responsive urban soundscapes. This directly aligns with NEB's mission of designing spaces that are not only more sustainable but also more conducive to human well-being. Sound, as a cultural and technological element, plays a critical role in shaping how we experience cities, public spaces, and even homes. By bringing together stakeholders from the tech sector, urban planning, and cultural industries, the event fosters collaborative experimentation that can lead to the development of NEB-compliant solutions for urban living environments.

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JUST Industry Data Week also serves as a platform for expanding NEB’s principles of sustainability and inclusion into new domains. For instance, participants engage in hands-on experiments using data from the Swedish Space Data Lab, health sector data platforms, and urban AI applications. These cross-domain activities are designed to bridge the gap between different industries and knowledge areas, promoting NEB values in a diverse range of contexts. This not only facilitates the creation of new, inclusive digital tools but also ensures that these innovations are deeply embedded in local living environments.

Additionally, the focus on data ethics and AI for social good is directly relevant to NEB’s objective of creating spaces that are not just physically sustainable, but also socially equitable and inclusive. The discussions during JUST Industry Data Week will explore how AI models can be trained and applied in ways that respect privacy, fairness, and inclusivity, ensuring that digital innovations benefit all citizens equally. By integrating AI and data ethics into NEB’s broader mission, the event will generate solutions that are both technologically advanced and ethically grounded, thus supporting the NEB community’s ongoing efforts to build sustainable, inclusive, and aesthetically pleasing living environments.

The cross-domain collaborations fostered by JUST Industry Data Week provide a crucial advantage to the NEB community by expanding the application of NEB principles beyond traditional sectors. These collaborations will help develop holistic, data-driven approaches to designing and managing living environments that fully integrate sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics—fulfilling the core objectives of the New European Bauhaus.

4. Target Stakeholder Groups

Seven stakeholder groups were selected to lead the engagement within the NEB community. Each of these groups brings their perspective, expertise, and skills to the project and are involved in different ways. The Stakeholder Groups (SGs) have been identified to create a comprehensive network that facilitates interactions between digital and New European Bauhaus players. Details about the Engagement Plan for each SG are presented in Chapter 4. The table below provides a more detailed overview of the relevant stakeholders involved and related multiplier networks to maximise engagement.

Figure 1: Engagement of all target stakeholder groups

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The stakeholder engagement strategies outlined in *D4.1* provided a structured approach for engaging distinct target groups, such as architects, urban planners, and community organisers. However, as the project has progressed, it has become evident that there is significant fluidity between these groups, driven by overlapping interests, cross-sectoral knowledge, and an increasing recognition that challenges within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) ecosystem require interdisciplinary solutions.

4.1. Evolving Stakeholder Group Dynamics

One of the most striking developments in the engagement process has been the natural overlap between stakeholder groups (SGs) originally considered distinct. For instance, architects involved in sustainable urban design often wear multiple hats, contributing not only as designers but also as educators, policy influencers, and digital innovators. This intersection of roles has blurred the boundaries between stakeholder categories, with many contributors actively engaging across several domains.

A notable development is the successful integration of stakeholder groups from outside those originally listed in the proposal, confirming the relevance of the junction between the NEB and the digital. A particularly notable example is the health sector's growing interest in the NEB framework. Health professionals, drawn by the intersection of environmental factors such as air quality and public health outcomes, are increasingly contributing to discussions around the built environment and its impact on well-being. This overlap has expanded the project's reach and demonstrated the wider applicability of NEB's principles, especially regarding how digital tools and data-driven solutions can be leveraged to improve both environmental and health outcomes.

4.2. Expanding the Target Stakeholder Groups

As a result of these cross-sectoral engagements, the original target SGs have broadened. This expansion is driven by the increasing recognition that solutions developed within the NEB ecosystem, such as AI tools for environmental monitoring or digital platforms for urban planning, have relevance beyond their initial fields of application.

While *D4.1* primarily focused on engaging architects, designers, urban planners, and construction professionals, the project has seen growing participation from experts in the fields of health, digital ethics, and data science. For example, air quality monitoring, initially considered within the domain of environmental and urban design, has attracted the attention of health professionals and researchers interested in how built environments influence public health. This broader inclusion of stakeholders from the health sector highlights the potential of NEB tools to drive innovation in unexpected but crucial areas, further expanding the project's scope and impact.

This widening of SGs is also reflected in the recruitment strategies for DigiNEB's digital focus groups and activities. Invitations to participate have been extended not only to core NEB contributors, such as members of the External Advisory Board (EAB) and professional associations within the NEB ecosystem, but also to professionals from sectors previously considered outside the project's original scope. This approach has helped bridge the gaps between different SGs and facilitated greater cross-pollination of ideas. This intersection of a broader representation of communities and specialisms has been anticipated as part of the DigiNEB day (and with involvement in other days) at the JUST Industry Data Week at Linköping Science Park.

digINEB at the JUST Data Week

Date & Time: 20 September 2024, 10:00-19:00

Venue: Online

Registration: [Register here](#)

[DigiNEB](#) is hosting a dedicated day focused on **data and AI applications for social good**, with a specific emphasis on enhancing the quality of life in living environments at [JUST Data Week](#), which aims to establish Judicious, Un-biased, Safe and Transparent (JUST) data practices as a complement to FAIR data.

The day will explore **how data-driven systems and technologies can transform urban spaces**, featuring insights from the NEB community and beyond, and reflect on JUST Data practices, emphasizing hands-on, collaborative methods for innovation across sectors like the built environment, transportation, healthcare, and earth observation.

Main highlights of the digINEB day:

✓ **10:00 Keynote on Benevolence and Invention**

Robert Cailliau, CERN Fellow and co-creator of the World Wide Web.

✓ **13:30 Launch of the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation**

After two years of research, collaboration, and iterative development, the digINEB project is ready to launch the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation. The handbook aims to **foster sustainable, locally-situated and inclusive regional development** across Europe and it provides innovative ideas and practical implementation, ensuring that regional innovation is rooted in the values of sustainability, inclusivity, and democratic participation.

✓ **18:00 Launch of the Susan Lesley Bland Prize for Social Good**

Presented by Robert Cailliau, the Susan Lesley Bland Prize for Social Good will be **awarded for applications and prototypes** created during a week of prototyping in urban environments using NEB methodologies.

Promotion of the DigiNEB Day at JUST Data Week through the European Commission's New European Bauhaus Community email newsletter

4.3. Impact of Fluidity on Engagement and Adoption

The growing fluidity between stakeholder groups has a positive effect on both engagement and the adoption of DigiNEB's digital tools. Stakeholders from diverse backgrounds see the relevance of NEB tools in their own contexts, even if those tools were originally designed for other domains. This cross-domain interest is a significant development, as it opens the door for broader adoption of DigiNEB platforms across new industries. The fluidity between SGs not only enhances the relevance of DigiNEB's offerings but also supports a more collaborative and interdisciplinary approach to solving the complex challenges that NEB seeks to address. As more stakeholders from diverse fields engage with the project, the potential for innovative solutions that bridge the gap between disciplines continues to grow.

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

This dynamic interaction among stakeholders has also influenced the content of key deliverables, such as the *DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap* and the *Ethics Report*, ensuring that insights from a wider range of experts are incorporated into the project’s strategic planning. The involvement of diverse sector professionals, digital ethics experts, and others from outside the initial SGs has enriched the project’s understanding of the broader societal impact of NEB solutions, positioning DigiNEB.eu as a platform that supports interdisciplinary collaboration at its core.

5. Engagement Channels: Summary of Updated Plan

Since the submission of *D4.1*, the strategic methodologies outlined in DigiNEB’s engagement and adoption plan have significantly evolved to reflect the changing dynamics of community interactions and the insights gained from the early phases of the project. The initial strategies, while effective in laying the foundation for stakeholder engagement, have been refined to better address the challenges and opportunities that have emerged.

- **A key development has been the recognition that in-person and hybrid gatherings of the DigiNEB community are essential for fostering deeper collaboration and co-creation.** With the easing of restrictions following the COVID-19 pandemic, these gatherings have become more feasible and are now being prioritised as central components of DigiNEB’s engagement strategy. In-person events and meetings organised on behalf of DigiNEB by External Advisory Board Members and the 6-day JUST Industry Data Week in Linköping reflect this shift toward hybrid formats, allowing for both face-to-face and digital participation.
- **The project’s updated strategy called for upgrading traditional social media channels to ones that encourage deeper learning and knowledge transfer.** It became clear that traditional social media approaches were no longer sufficient to sustain meaningful engagement. By shifting the focus from simple content dissemination to interactive, educational platforms, DigiNEB aims to foster more impactful and lasting engagement within its community.
- **A priority in this updated plan is engaging EU regions through the transfer of methodologies that support collaborative learning and innovation.** This updated plan incorporates revisions to the engagement channels, introducing new methodologies that prioritise collaborative learning, co-creation, and innovation. It also includes new tools, such as the revamped DigiNEB website, the *NEB Concepts* podcast, and the *Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation*, all of which are designed to facilitate both policy influence and community-driven innovation. These enhancements ensure that DigiNEB remains adaptable and responsive to the evolving needs of the NEB community.

5.1. Project identity update

The DigiNEB project has undergone a visual and conceptual identity update to better reflect the evolving nature of its role within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) ecosystem. The new project identity draws inspiration from the traditional and digital tools used by architects and planners, positioning DigiNEB as a blueprint for future NEB interactions in the digital space.

The updated logo and branding incorporate design elements that evoke architectural schematics and planning blueprints, symbolising DigiNEB's commitment to creating structured yet flexible digital solutions for sustainability, innovation, and inclusion. This visual language emphasises the project's focus on bridging the physical and digital realms, aligning with the NEB's goal of reimagining spaces and environments in ways that harmonise aesthetics, function, and ecological responsibility. The identity not only reflects the project's current activities but also its vision for the future—serving as a guiding framework for digital transformation in the built environment.

The identity is a collaborative effort between project partners with multiple layers added by different stakeholders to indicate evolving collaborations.

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5.2. DigiNEB Website (DigiNEB.eu)

THE DigiNEB INITIATIVE

Digital Tools

Digital Tools for

Digital Projects

Projects that develop

E-learning

E-learning and training

Open Licences

Open Licenses for

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

The relaunched DigiNEB website serves as the cornerstone of the updated engagement strategy, offering a more intuitive user experience, improved navigation, and new features designed to enhance knowledge transfer and collaboration.

THE DigiNEB INITIATIVE

Digital Tools

Digital Tools for Architects, Designers and Communities

Digital Projects

Projects that develop Digital Tools or Innovations that can support the Objectives of NEB

E-learning

E-learnings and training modules

Open Licences

Open Licenses for Data and Content that can be freely used, modified, and shared

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

5.3. Digital Focus Groups (formerly TWGs)

The DigiNEB.eu platform embeds and disseminates the interdisciplinary Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) as Digital Focus Groups under the broad overarching themes of 1) Design & Architecture, 2) Production & Construction, 3) Verticals, and 4) Community & Sustainability and AI. These groups bring together stakeholder experts and broader community contributors into the DigiNEB.eu ecosystem.

In line with the updated Description of Action for reaching the objectives of the project, top level experts are invited for consultation in the digital technical groups. Desk research on the representative stakeholders was conducted, including both internal stakeholders, such as the members of the EAB and members affiliated to the professional associations who are project partners in the consortium, external stakeholders, such as professionals with a background in early and visible adoption of digital solutions, entities engaging in civic engagement, members in professional communities and professional associations within the broader New European Bauhaus community.

For reaching the desired number of participants we aimed for an initial sample of 3 times the number of desired participants. As such, an average of 20 invitations were sent for each group, from EU member states and associated countries.

Other recruitment strategies included disseminating the TWGs / Digital Focus Groups in:

- the NEB newsletter through the European contact point for NEB;
- the NEB community platform calendar of events;
- presentation given in the European Federation for Living Social Topic Group;
- the TU Delft AI initiative

The input from the four thematic digital technical working groups have also fed into the following deliverables:

- D.1.4. Ethics report.
- D.2.5. Landscape report and gap analysis – final version.
- D5.3. DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap.

The Digital Focus Groups are open to all stakeholders and form a focal point of stakeholder engagement. They are organised around thematic areas developed with the NEB community, and add to the workshops organised in WP5, producing a series of reports on landscape and gap analysis, best practices and other relevant topics. The groups also contribute to networking events. Community co-creation help evolve and shape the thematic areas listed in the DigiNEB proposal:

- Design & Architecture
 - Enhancing biodiversity; eco-systemic decision-making in design
 - Circular Design, design for disassembly/deconstruction
 - Morphology of human settlements: organising the relationship of urbanity and rurality
 - Architectural-data cycles for sustainable design qualities
 - Sustainable design of the rural area
 - Creative design & project environment
 - Biogenic carbon storage: designing buildings and cities as carbon banks
- Production & Construction
 - Digitising the building sector: applications throughout building and urban life cycles (online presence, VR, home automation, etc.)
 - Technologies for a sustainable construction industry
 - Engineered biomaterials and novel building products for construction
 - Additive manufacturing and CNC cutting

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- Technologies for a sustainable textiles industry & other innovative materials
- Creative startups
- Verticals
 - Healthy living environment and buildings for health(care)
 - Education
 - Future-proof heritage
 - Existing housing stock and infrastructure
 - Building manufacturing
 - Building & mobility
- Community & Sustainability
 - People and their communities: user-centred criteria/participatory design processes for sustainable and smart urbanisation
 - Fair and just transitions: equity and empowerment for disenfranchised populations
 - Biogenic carbon storage: buildings and cities as carbon banks
 - Energy transition and climate adaptation in the construction industry
 - Impact assessment: gathering data and tracking our footprints
 - Ending waste: policies and practices in a circular construction economy

5.4. Upgrading Social Media Approaches

The project's approach to social media has evolved to better support collaborative learning and knowledge transfer. While traditional social media channels played a role in the initial phases of the project and will continue to do so to a lesser extent, they have proven limited in fostering sustained engagement. The updated strategy moves beyond ephemeral content to dynamic and persistent content, including interactive dialogues that encourage deeper learning and stakeholder participation.

The project initially encountered limited success with static content dissemination, particularly on platforms such as Instagram, which did not foster the level of interaction needed to support the NEB community's goals. Social media will be leveraged to announce publications, podcast releases and policy contributions, but they are supportive rather than central, encouraging stakeholders to more deeply engage with the substantive outputs and more enduring media dissemination and knowledge exchange initiatives of the project.

As a result of the upgraded approach, the KPIs outlined in the original plan have been revised, as they tended only to measure quantity of output such as numbers of posts on particular platforms, rather than more meaningful indicators or strategies for engagement by and with the NEB Community.

5.5. Podcast: NEB Concepts

NEB Concepts

NEB Concepts features insightful conversations with leading architects, educators, and project leaders. The discussions deal with topics at the intersection of sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design. You'll hear directly from those shaping the future of urban development, cultural heritage, and community empowerment.

NEB Concepts is modular – it allows you to 'choose your own adventure': follow the links and tags to explore themes such as climate adaptation, technology integration, and interdisciplinary collaboration – or stick with the wide-ranging thoughts of a single interviewee.

Each short episode provides a collection of ideas and practices, projects and reflections, highlighting the transformative potential of the New European Bauhaus for a more inclusive and sustainable future.

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Recognising the gap left by the social media disconnect described in 4.3 above, a key adaptation in the updated plan is the creation of the *NEB Concepts* podcast. Although producing a podcast was not required by the original DOA, it has been introduced as a direct response to the challenges faced in generating sustained engagement through traditional social media channels.

The podcast was developed as a dynamic and educational tool that can engage a broad audience.

The modular nature of the series allows users to explore topics based on their interests, such as sustainability, technology integration, or interdisciplinary collaboration. By offering deeper and more flexible content, the podcast provides a more robust and enduring medium for engagement, helping to overcome the limitations of more ephemeral social media interactions. This ensures that the NEB community and stakeholders have access to sustained learning experiences that directly support the project's long-term objectives.

The *NEB Concepts* series features structured conversations with key figures within the wider New European Bauhaus community, including architects, educators, project leaders, and members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board. These discussions are divided into 57 episodes, each exploring topics at the intersection of sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design, reflecting the multidisciplinary nature of the NEB initiative.

***NEB Concepts* is designed to provide insights into the evolving discourse surrounding the New European Bauhaus, and in particular the intersection of digital technologies and tools with the NEB ecosystem.** Each episode offers a focused exploration of themes such as climate adaptation, digitalisation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and community engagement. The modular nature of the series allows listeners to engage with content in a manner that suits their interests, whether by exploring individual topics in depth or following the perspectives of specific interviewees. This initiative contributes to the broader goals of DigiNEB by offering an additional medium for disseminating knowledge and fostering dialogue among stakeholders.

NEB Concepts

NEB Concepts is a podcast that features insightful **conversations with leading architects, educators, and project leaders.**

The discussions deal with topics at the **intersection of sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design.** You'll hear directly from those shaping the future of urban development, cultural heritage, and community empowerment.

Explore the guests and collection of ideas and practices, projects and reflections discussed [here](#).

The NEB Concepts podcast was promoted to the NEB Community through the official New European Bauhaus Community email newsletter published by the European Commission.

The episodes also serve as a resource for various educational and professional development contexts, supporting the continuous learning objectives of the NEB initiative.

Key Participants:

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The *NEB Concepts* series includes contributions from several prominent figures within the NEB ecosystem, including:

- Aase Højlund Nielsen
- Andreja Kutnar
- Davor Meersman
- Francesca Rizzo
- Frank van der Hoeven
- Jan Bunge
- Markus Reymann
- Matti Kuittinen
- Mia Roth Cerina
- Roberto Cavallo
- Selma Harrington
- Sheela Patel

These individuals are leaders of NEB Lighthouse projects, members of the NEB High-Level Round Table, and distinguished members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board. Their participation in the podcast series ensures that the content reflects a diverse range of perspectives and expertise.

The *NEB Concepts* series is intended to complement other stakeholder engagement activities within the DigiNEB project. By providing a platform for in-depth discussions on critical topics, the series supports the project’s objective of facilitating interdisciplinary knowledge exchange and fostering a shared understanding of NEB principles. Additionally, the series is positioned as an educational tool that can be integrated into academic curricula, workshops, and professional training programs, thereby extending its impact beyond the immediate project consortium and existing stakeholder community.

5.6. Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation

The updated plan also places a strong emphasis on the transfer of methodologies for collaborative learning and innovation, particularly to EU regions. This strategy is encapsulated in the *Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation*, a resource designed to engage regional authorities and community leaders in applying NEB principles to their local contexts.

Building on the the handbook prototype presented in deliverable D4.1 and incorporating co-creation methodologies from across NEB initiatives and best practices from other projects, the handbook provides practical guidance on co-creation, participatory design, and regional innovation, helping to bridge the gap between established NEB hubs and emerging regions. The *Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation* intends to serve as a practical guide for local and regional policymakers, civic leaders, and community stakeholders. The handbook is designed to facilitate the application of New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles—sustainability, inclusion, and aesthetics—within specific regional contexts, using collaborative learning and co-creation methodologies developed through the DigiNEB.eu project.

The first version, a “Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook”, builds on the New European Bauhaus success stories that have featured at the NEB Festival (the Duved Project presented with

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Commissioner Ferreira) and NEB initiatives supported by National Governments (The “Norrlands Model” and “Visions in the North”). The prototype introduces a reimagined framework based on Walter Gropius’ 1922 Bauhaus circle diagram, adapted for modern societal challenges. It positions the local as the focal point of future development, advocating for decentralised, ecosystemic approaches that emphasise collaboration across diverse fields. The handbook suggests a holistic, inclusive model where co-creation, sustainability, and participatory processes drive innovation. It highlights the need for interconnected systems, addressing climate change, democracy, and local resilience through shared knowledge, regenerative practices, and cross-disciplinary dialogue.

This updated approach aims to foster local ecosystems that integrate specialised knowledge into broader contexts, ensuring that local communities take active roles in societal development. By utilising tools like the circular economy and zero-waste principles, this ecosystemic model seeks to generate synergies that support sustainable growth, resilience, and innovation across sectors such as food systems, housing, and public spaces. The handbook ultimately offers a flexible blueprint for community-driven societal transformation, tailored to the specific challenges and opportunities of each unique context.

The “Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook” was launched at a public event at the Faculty of Architecture at Umeå University on 9th February 2024 entitled “The Local is the Future”. The event was introduced by Cornelia Redeker, Head Of Architecture, University of Umeå. The panel included Helene Hellmark-Knutsson, Governor of Västerbotten County and former Swedish Minister of Education; Jan Åman, author of the Norrlands Model and Prototype of an Ecosystemic Handbook (partner ICF); Michela Magas, Member of the NEB High Level Round Table (partner ICF); Sara Thor, Lecturer in Architecture at Umeå School of Architecture; Adam Davies, Co-Founder of sustainable design agency Tÿ Syml and co-author of the “Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook”; and Magnus Myrenberg, Partner at Aalto Capital.

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The prototype handbook, which forms much of the basis of the developed Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation, was launched at a public event at the Faculty of Architecture at Umeå University on 9th February 2024.

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This initial prototype evolved from NEB community projects has been evolved and amplified to include work by the Joint Research Centre and methodologies developed and tested by the NEB Lab and NEB Lighthouse projects. The DigiNEB Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation builds on the work of its predecessor and incorporates co-creation methodologies from across the wider NEB community. Stakeholders are invited to contribute their tools and approaches to be incorporated into the final version, which will be presented to the JRC and the European Committee of the Regions in the final month of the project. In so doing, the project aims to transfer successful digital and co-creation methodologies from established NEB hubs to emerging regions, supporting broader and more inclusive engagement across Europe. By focusing on the transfer of successful methodologies, the handbook supports DigiNEB's goal of expanding the reach and impact of NEB principles and digital strategies across Europe.

5.7. Engaging Communities in Policymaking

A strategic development to the engagement plan involves collaborating directly with the NEB Community of experts in policymaking through collaborative authorship. By encouraging stakeholders to contribute to joint White Papers, policy recommendations, and other publications, DigiNEB aims to empower community members to influence policy development at regional, national, and EU levels.

A key milestone in this process was the engagement by DigiNEB of the NEB community around the NEB Mission by engaging Member States to support the NEB Mission at the Council of Europe on the 12th of September 2023. A strategic in-person meeting was organised with the NEB team on the 21 September 2023 that contributed to the strategic direction for the NEB. A White Paper authored in collaboration with NEB Lab, NEB Lighthouse, and digiNEB EAB provided content towards the establishment of the NEB Facility, the crosscutting funding vehicle for the future of the NEB.

DigiNEB EAB members organised Policy meetings, for instance a workshop held in Zagreb by the Croatian Society of Architects.

The DigiNEB Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation directly engages policymakers and regional administrators in co-creation methodologies to apply best practices from the New European Bauhaus ecosystem to engage local communities in fostering improved living environments through digital and social technologies and innovations.

DigiNEB engaged leaders of NEB Labs and NEB Lighthouses in regular meetings, to co-author a White Paper, intended to guide the NEB Mission's future direction and evolution towards the NEB Facility. The community agreed at the NEB@CERN event to co-author a white paper to guide the NEB towards future funding. This continued at dedicated workshops and meetings organised by the members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board, NEB Lab and NEB Lighthouse thought leaders.

The White Paper, written by thought leaders from across the NEB community, presents a comprehensive vision for the future of NEB. It serves as a foundational document that will continue to drive policy discussions and shape the future of NEB-related initiatives.

The White Paper not only highlights the wide-ranging perspectives of DigiNEB thought leaders but also emphasises the practical steps needed to build a sustainable and inclusive digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus. One of the key themes across several contributions is the integration of **co-creation methodologies** that foster collaboration between regional authorities, communities, and digital innovators. The White Paper also underlines the importance of **data ethics and governance**,

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advocating for transparency in digital innovation to ensure that NEB principles—sustainability, inclusiveness, and aesthetics—are reflected in both technological development and policy frameworks. Additionally, there is a strong focus on leveraging existing NEB Lighthouse projects as scalable models for other regions, ensuring that the NEB digital ecosystem can be tailored to different local contexts while maintaining core European values. The paper stresses the need for interdisciplinary collaboration, calling for enhanced dialogue between the public, private, and research sectors to create an ecosystem that is not only innovative but also aligned with the mission of the New European Bauhaus.

Excerpt from the White Paper

Editor's Note

This White Paper is written in response to the European Commission working paper 'First Reflections on Building Blocks for the Design of a Possible EU Mission on the New European Bauhaus'. The contributing authors are thought leaders from the DigiNEB community – the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus. They include members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board and leaders of NEB Lighthouse projects. Representatives of this community first came together during the DigiNEB event NEB@CERN 27 February – 1 March 2023 and, in a series of workshops, started to develop a comprehensive vision for the development of the New European Bauhaus digital ecosystem. A productive meeting about the NEB Mission was organised by DigiNEB with representatives from the NEB unit at the JRC in Zagreb on the 20th and 21st of September, 2023. This White Paper starts by referring to the original vision by President von der Leyen and the Concept Paper by the NEB High Level Round Table (HLRT) and proceeds to the contributions of the listed authors.

We adopted a pluralistic approach to capturing the voices of the community, representing sometimes differing views, and most importantly, not cancelling each other out. Each EAB member or lighthouse leader who was asked to contribute was tasked with creating a 1-2 pager on their positioning in respect of the NEB Mission. Each positioning was added as a separate chapter. Contributors could work together or amplify each other's vision, by agreement with the authors. Aside from small edits, contributions are left intact demonstrating a multiplicity of views and diversity of approaches. All are valid, and seldom contradictory. We have at times suggested more effective wording to convey the message, but we have allowed for a democratic representation of all the core voices from the community.

This White Paper is included as an annex to this deliverable.

digineb White Paper

on the future of NEB in Horizon Programmes

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Framing the NEB vision

When President von der Leyen launched the New European Bauhaus in her inaugural State of the Union speech on the 16th of September 2020, it was the first time that she called for a "co-creation space where architects, artists, students, engineers, designers work together". This call to create a multidisciplinary movement for co-creation is significant because, for the first time, she called for **translation of thought into practice** through the **prototyping of tangible solutions** that could turn into **evidence-based policy**.

A group of practitioners were invited as the President's High Level Round Table to translate their practice into a Concept for the New European Bauhaus. The first HLRT activity identified a strong "**line of justice**" that cut through all foundational values. Mapping desired outcomes was united by a strong concept of "**learning by doing**". Social justice and

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In addition to the White Paper, a repository was created using Notion as an outcome of the CERN event, as a community resource. This platform has enabled ongoing collaboration, with the community continuing to interact regularly, hosted by sister projects such as CrAft and the NEB Academy. This approach aligns with the NEB's commitment to participatory innovation and builds on the NEB method by combining scientific rigour with grassroots-driven insights. Community-driven policy input is gathered through events, the website, and social media channels, ensuring broad and diverse participation in shaping the future of NEB-related policies.

5.8. Educational Strategy

One of DigiNEB's objectives is capacity-building across the European Union. Using the networks of the EAAE, the project engaged educational channels to promote innovation and collaboration within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) community. During the activities and engagements realised, significant progress was made in aligning educational efforts with the needs of the NEB community. The educational strategy emanates from work package 3 and its tasks: Training programme, Transferring innovation best practices and Early Adopters network. These tasks support each other to create a digital and physical ecosystem of exchange. DigiNEB relied on activities and events where the project connected with the NEB Community and Stakeholders to create collaborative spaces to learn from each other's experiences and practices. A comprehensive list of these activities can be found in deliverable 3.3.

A combination of webinars, Thematic Working Groups and workshops in collaboration with the partner's networks ensured that DigiNEB could collect and spread innovation best practices while engaging with the NEB Community and other networks. Furthermore, DigiNEB developed a training programme that showcases existing learning resources aligned with the NEB.

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5.9. Training Programme and NEB Academy

The first pillar of the education strategy is the training programme: a compilation of learning resources supporting the upskilling of the NEB Community related to the NEB Values. We monitored the existing learning resources and finally made an inventory showing the gaps and overlaps. Parallel to the project, the NEB Academy initiative was launched strengthening the relevance of this task. The DigiNEB project supported the NEB Academy from its ideation through workshops in the CERN IdeaSquare Event. Later, partners actively participated in the NEB Academy launch in Slovenia leveraging and sharpening our educational strategy. Furthermore, TU Delft oversaw the initiation of the NEB Academy digital platform demo, engaging various NEB partners in its co-creation and testing including Nordic Bauhaus members'. Finally, DigiNEB will have a strong impact in the future of the NEB Academy.

5.10. Workshops

Workshops are physical or online events to facilitate discussions and co-creation between Smart Communities and the New European Bauhaus stakeholders. The DigiNEB team exceeded its intended delivery of six hands-on co-creation workshops as part of the CERN event. The format delivered was based on best practice from NEB co-creation processes and has been shown to produce greater value for the community.

The DigiNEB project initially planned to primarily deliver webinars. However, as the project progressed, numerous webinars and in-person workshops were delivered, fostering collaboration and engagement with stakeholders across various fields.

A full list of over 40 workshops, seminars, community events, keynotes and other engagements is listed in D3.3. These include sessions on 'How can timber construction and digitalisation boost the New European Bauhaus?', 'How can we register ideas in the Creative industries?' and keynote speeches at the launch of the Swedish Presidency of the Council of the EU.

DigiNEB has facilitated clustering and convergence on common themes and challenges, fostered the exchange of good practices, and identified how digital transformation can contribute to implementing digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus community projects. The workshops have been recorded and the knowledge gathered is distributed through dissemination.

Part of the strategy for greater community engagement is the leveraging of larger-scale events and notable project partnerships to attract participation. The multi-day dedicated physical workshop organised in partnership with CERN that was hosted at CERN IdeaSquare gathered over 50 DigiNEB community stakeholders.

5.11. Updated Plan and Timeline: Phases 1 and 2

The project timeline has been updated to reflect the phased approach:

- **Phase 1 (M1-14):** Establishing core engagement strategies, launching the website, and building the foundation of the DigiNEB community.
- **Phase 2 (M15-27):** Expanding the strategic methodologies, launching new tools like the podcast and handbook, and prioritising in-person and hybrid events for deeper engagement.

This two-phase approach allows for the continuous evolution of the engagement plan, ensuring that it remains responsive to the needs of the NEB community and adaptable to emerging trends in digital innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration.

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5.12. DigiNEB Early Adopters

DigiNEB leverages the interest and engagement of early adopters of the DigiNEB platform for further outreach. The DigiNEB Early Adopters are champions who use digital solutions and act as ambassadors or enthusiastic mediators between the creators of the tools and their own wider communities. Such champions help community-building processes by facilitating community interaction and onboarding broader communities.

The strategy for onboarding Early Adopters has been to focus on NEB thought leaders. This has proven successful already in the early stages of the project. All have continued to be active contributors to the direction, content and organisation of in-person workshops and meetings. A selection of thought leaders have contributed to the *NEB Concepts* podcast series. This content is also made available (under granted & referenced permission), promoted and highlighted on the DigiNEB platform as a reference for the DigiNEB community.

5.13. External Advisory Board

The External Advisory Board connects DigiNEB with proactive, eminent stakeholders with thought leadership and influence. The EAB was established to provide competent and independent guidance to the project while at the same time supporting both thematic working groups and the NEB catalogue through roadmap recommendations. These advisors can provide the project with timely knowledge (technical, policy and innovation) to support content and outputs (i.e., roadmap, policy briefs, Digital Focus Group reports) and impact policy, industry and research.

The DigiNEB EAB has been notably very active, has offered both expert guidance, as well as hands-on contributions and organisation of events and activities. The EAB covers accessibility, architecture, design and construction materials. It comprises 16 renowned and esteemed EAB members (eight women and eight men) who have agreed to bring their expertise to the DigiNEB community. Below is a complete list of the External Advisory Board members:

- **Michela Magas** (Chair), Partner DigiNEB Industry Commons Foundation
- **Christina Claeson-Jonsson**, Director of Research and Development at NCC AB, construction industry
- **Annette Hafner**, Professor at Ruhr-Universität Bochum
- **Selma Harrington**, Executive Board Member at The Architects' Council of Europe (ACE)
- **Dimitris Kiritsis**, Professor of ICT and Sustainable Manufacturing at EPFL (École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne)
- **Matti Kuittinen**, Professor at Aalto University and former Senior Ministerial Advisor at the Ministry of the Environment of Finland
- **Andreja Kutnar**, Director at InnoRenew CoE
- **Martin Luce**, Director at TUM School of Engineering and Design
- **Tom Minderhoud**, Sensor Architect at UNStudio
- **Kirsi Mustalahti**, Founder & Chairwoman at ACCAC Global
- **Fredrik Nilsson**, Professor, Vice President of Campus and Sustainable Development at Chalmers University of Technology
- **Alan Organschi**, Director at Bauhaus Earth
- **Sheela Patel**, Grassroots Global Activist at International Institute for Environment and Development
- **Ignasi Pérez Arnal**, Director at REBUILD Congress
- **Francesca Rizzo**, Full Professor at Politecnico di Milano
- **Mia Roth-Čerina**, Vice-Dean for International Relations and Art at the University of Zagreb

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- **Ruth Schagemann**, President of the Architects’ Council of Europe (ACE-CAE)
- **Jose Pedro Sousa**, Associate Professor at the University of Porto and Member of the NEB HLRT.

As shown in the list above, each individual has been selected from diverse organisations and research institutions to cater for a broad domain range and balanced geographical distribution. Experts were chosen for their experience and roles as advisors or experts in sectoral innovation, market needs, government policies and societal impact. They reflect the different NEB stakeholders and include experts in architecture, accessibility, construction, design, engineering, and national and regional policy. EAB members have affiliations with prestigious institutions, including Yale University, the Architect’s Council of Europe, and the Ministry of the Environment of Finland. They have been selected to ensure a comprehensive representation of the Stakeholder Groups and create fundamental synergistic relationships with external institutions and organisations to facilitate the learning & transfer process.

Figure 8: DigiNEB External Advisory Board comprises multidisciplinary experts from Sweden, Germany, Switzerland, Finland, Slovenia, Croatia, Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Portugal and India.

5.14. NEB community and NEB Academy

The DigiNEB team has established a good working relationship and continuous dialogue with the NEB communication team at the JRC to ensure that the DigiNEB communication strategy is aligned with that of the New European Bauhaus. The DigiNEB and NEB teams communicate via emails or video calls and present the main topics to be carried out in the next month, summarised in a collaborative online document. The cooperation between DigiNEB and the NEB team helps each to multiply the impacts of their work and reach a wider audience.

More information on the communication flow between DigiNEB and NEB is described in the deliverable *D5.1 Plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities (DECP)* in month 6.

The main DigiNEB goal is to develop the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus, which, as discussed above, comprises:

- **Digital Toolkit:** a catalogue with over 200 digital solutions for the NEB ecosystem;

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- **Observatory:** a collection of EU-funded initiatives and success stories to raise awareness of NEB programmes and the benefits of digital solutions, as well as to encourage collaborations;
- **eLearning catalogue:** a collaborative online set of courses and training materials aimed at stimulating knowledge and sharing best practices.

DigiNEB continues to liaise with New European Bauhaus initiatives, NEB partners and NEB Lighthouse projects on the development of the NEB Academy. The project invites existing groups already connected with New European Bauhaus activities to use the platform to gather, connect and share knowledge.

6. Stakeholder Engagement Plan

The present Stakeholder Engagement Plan includes all activities that the DigiNEB consortium aims to implement in its lifetime to connect with identified SGs and ensure their interaction is mutually beneficial.

Engagement with stakeholders is an activity that involves all members of the DigiNEB consortium. Partners each contribute to upskilling, upscaling and leveraging existing projects. Linking with partners’ existing networks and connections is an essential aspect of this outreach, as well as ensuring that digital divide and data literacy issues are addressed within stakeholder-specific domains. In addition, each partner has a specific focal area, in part to share the workload and leverage key strengths but also to avoid duplication.

The role played by each partner is summarised in the table below:

Partner name	Engagement role and responsibility
Delft University of Technology (TU Delft)	The partner is the primary contact for creating the DigiNEB Thematic Working Groups. TU Delft provides, as the main outcome, the development of landscape and gap reports and contribution to the strategic DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap. In the amended and updated DigiNEB plan, TU Delft has taken over the design and management of the website platform. Furthermore, TU Delft is engaged in three NEB Lighthouse projects (CULTUURCAMPUS, NEB-STAR, and DESIRE), ensuring a smooth dialogue with them.
Industry Commons Foundation (ICF)	ICF brings together an extensive network of over 8500 cross-domain stakeholders and experts in cross-domain collaboration. The ICF work in digital solutions for large industry players enables a strong connection between NEB and the digital transformation. ICF Director of Research, Michela Magas, is a member of President von der Leyen’s High Level Round Table for NEB, and is closely connected to the thought leaders of the NEB Labs and Lighthouse projects, as well as NEB Partners and Friends of NEB. As Member of the CERN Advisory Board, she is able to leverage the connection between NEB and CERN.
European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE)	EAAE is one of the main contributors to scout and recruit Early Adopters of the NEB Digital Ecosystem. The team also contributes to adding relevant content for the eLearning courses included in the NEB Academy.
InnovaWood (IW)	The partner has a strong experience in NEB-related initiatives connected to sustainable wood and forestry construction and bio-based materials and acts as one of the leading players in creating engagement towards the stakeholders involved in this field. Moreover, InnovaWood is instrumental in seeking training and digital solutions related to the forestry industry.

Table 4 - Engagement roles and responsibilities played by the DigiNEB consortium

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The coordination among all the partners involved is ensured via periodic meetings. The coordination ensures the implementation of a dedicated plan, differentiated by Stakeholder Group, as presented in the paragraphs below.

6.1. Plan and Timeline

The DigiNEB consortium performs dedicated campaigns to support the building of an engaged community through four distinct phases, as described during the proposal phase.

Figure 8: Campaigns and channels to engage with the stakeholders

Figure 8 shows the original plan. This plan has been updated with a new version of the website. The site has been relaunched by TU Delft to address the challenges that led to the project amendment and refocus of the initiative.

6.2. Stakeholder Groups

To ensure each Stakeholder Group (SG) is both engaged with and can contribute to shaping the NEB digital ecosystem, the consortium has updated its plan to maximise involvement across all groups. This engagement strategy emphasises interdisciplinary collaboration and alignment with the NEB initiative, inviting participants from all SGs to engage in shared activities such as the JUST Industry Data Week in Linköping and other interdisciplinary events. Below is the revised engagement plan for each group:

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Engagement Plan
SG#1	Architects, Designers, Engineers, and other professionals belonging to the NEB community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engaged through participation in the Early Adopters Programme, showcasing NEB-aligned digital solutions that have been adopted and successfully implemented. ● Encouraged to become active users of the Digital Toolkit and Observatory, which provide essential resources for NEB-aligned digital transformation. ● Upskilling opportunities provided via access to the NEB Academy, including eLearning courses aimed at enhancing their professional expertise.

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Engagement Plan
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in Digital Focus Group discussions, contributing to Landscape and Gap Reports that help define the scope of NEB innovation. • Invited to interdisciplinary events and workshops, where they can collaborate with other SGs to shape the NEB digital ecosystem.
SG#2	Construction industry suppliers & other relevant industry players, including start-ups, SMEs, associations in the building, mobility & health sectors, and SDOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure opportunities by contributing digital solutions to the Digital Toolkit, allowing their innovations to become potential success stories within the NEB ecosystem. • Gaining insights into the NEB digital landscape by interacting with other suppliers and learning about existing market solutions. • Offered skills development through access to the NEB Academy's eLearning resources. • Participating in interdisciplinary events and workshops, allowing cross-sector collaboration to better understand market needs and opportunities.
SG#3	Research and academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing the knowledge gap by both providing and accessing learning resources, particularly through the NEB eLearning platform. • Contributing to discussion groups and engaging with Landscape and Gap Reports to ensure that research outputs are aligned with the NEB ecosystem's needs. • Offering access to digital solutions developed in the context of R&I initiatives and EU-funded projects, fostering a bridge between research and real-world applications. • Actively participating in interdisciplinary workshops aimed at identifying future needs and gaps within the NEB digital ecosystem, collaborating with professionals from other SGs.
SG#4	Digital technology companies & associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provided exposure opportunities through contributions to the Digital Toolkit, with their digital solutions serving as case studies and success stories. • Given access to the NEB digital ecosystem, enabling them to assess and benchmark their offerings against other market solutions. • Skills development opportunities through participation in the NEB Academy's eLearning programmes, helping them stay ahead in digital innovation.

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Engagement Plan
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging in interdisciplinary workshops and events, fostering collaboration with other sectors to shape future needs within the NEB digital ecosystem.
SG#5	Policy Makers, including Green Deal-related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessing the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation, which serves as a foundation for shaping future policies that promote NEB-aligned digital environments at both European and local levels. Participating in interdisciplinary webinars and workshops, where they can collaborate with experts from various SGs to gain insights on policy perspectives and NEB-aligned digital transformation.
SG#6	National & regional authorities, mayors (including urban planners) and cities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributing digital solutions and success stories that showcase NEB-aligned innovations successfully implemented in cities, villages, and regional communities. Accessing the Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation, helping local authorities align with broader NEB policies while addressing specific regional needs. Engaging in interdisciplinary workshops, collaborating with other SGs to share local policy insights and practical approaches for applying NEB principles at the regional and local levels.
SG#7	Civil society organisations and citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invited to interdisciplinary webinars that focus on explaining the goals of DigiNEB and the broader NEB initiative, helping citizens understand how they can contribute to and benefit from these innovations. Accessing the resources made available via the NEB eLearning Catalogue, helping to reduce knowledge gaps and empowering citizens to engage with the NEB digital ecosystem.

Table 6 - Engagement plan per Stakeholder Group

An update to the strategy to engage Stakeholder Groups has been the project’s re-focus on interdisciplinary engagement and inviting participants from across all SGs to engage in DigiNEB activities, and in particular the JUST Data Week in Linköping.

7. Synergies

Sharing the benefits of developing the NEB Digital Ecosystem is a collaborative activity. Since the beginning of DigiNEB, the project team has established strong synergies with initiatives in the NEB and built environment domains to foster the adoption of digitalisation to create more inclusive, sustainable and beautiful living spaces.

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The following represents the types of initiatives DigiNEB aims to engage with, and the main achievements gathered in the first three months from its launch.

7.1. NEB Lighthouse projects

The NEB [Lighthouse projects](#) are demonstrators that can showcase the benefits and practicalities of applying the NEB's main goals locally. To date, the following 6 Lighthouse projects have been selected¹:

CULTUURCAMPUS: A sustainable hub of arts, research, learning and community as a catalyst. By blending education, research, policy, and culture and considering the lived experiences of its residents, Cultuurcampus aims to transform the disadvantaged urban area of Rotterdam South (NL). The Cultuurcampus is in a historic building and act as a hub for different groups and activities. (<https://www.cultuurencampusrotterdam.nl/en/>)

NEB-STAR (New European Bauhaus STAvangeR): NEB-STAR showcases how territorial transformation plans can incorporate the principles and values of the NEB in Stavanger (NO), Prague (CZ) and Utrecht (NL). The project tackles four emblematic challenges linked to climate-neutral cities, all considering local needs and concerns through co-creation with residents and stakeholders. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079952>)

NEBourhoods: NEBourhoods prepares Munich-Neuperlach (DE) for the future as mapped out by the European Green Deal regarding the built environment, circularity, mobility, energy, food, and health. The project builds on the area's strengths – a strong sense of community, vast green areas, and large-scale housing, even if in need of renovation – and address its weaknesses – higher than average unemployment and lower than average education levels. (<https://www.nebourhoods.de/>)

DESIRE (Designing the Irresistible Circular Society): the project wants to tackle the major challenges faced by societies and cities: climate change, biodiversity loss and resource challenges. Based on three main themes of inclusivity, circularity and reconciling cities with nature, the project uses art, architecture, and design to explore alternative ways of transforming territories across different European cities in Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy, Latvia and Slovenia. (<https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/>)

EHHUR (EYES HEARTS HANDS Urban Revolution): the project supports cities and vulnerable residents in transforming their built environment. Spread across seven different locations in the EU and Associated Countries (Denmark, Belgium, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Turkey, and Croatia), it seeks to tackle socioeconomic and cultural challenges such as social segregation, energy poverty, and degradation of depopulated historical centres. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079948>)

Bauhaus of the Seas: the project aims to promote renewed ethical and aesthetic regenerative development from a diverse range of dimensions of our continued relationship with the sea. Conceived as a journey with Portugal as a starting point, the Bauhaus of the Seas generates a design movement extending to all European coastal and maritime regions.

The NEB Lighthouse projects are engaged through dedicated workshops where the experts can bring their own experiences in cities, regions and nations to help implement the NEB principles thanks to digitalisation. The aim of the synergies is that, in turn, the lighthouse projects may utilise the various DigiNEB solutions to increase impact.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_2780

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All Lighthouse projects have been onboarded in the first part of the project, primarily through their involvement at the CERN event.

7.2. DigiNEB and sister CSA projects

DigiNEB started to engage with projects that share similarities in terms of communities and objectives in October 2022.

The two sister projects, which are CSAs, are DS4SSCC and Living in EU:

- [DS4SSCC](#) (Data Space for Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities) is an EU-funded initiative that prepares for the creation of a data space for smart communities as an enabler of the EU Green Deal goals and Sustainable Development Goals.
- [Living in EU](#): through co-creation with citizens, the project aims to bring the economic and social benefits of this transformation to all local communities and implement an inclusive digital Europe with powerful digital services, technologies, infrastructures and skills).

The three projects have established a collaboration task force in which the coordinators of the initiatives meet monthly to discuss synergies and cooperation activities. The main discussion points from the meeting are summarised in the minutes and actions to be delivered for the next meeting.

7.3. NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces projects

In addition to the abovementioned synergies, the DigiNEB consortium establishes synergies with stakeholders involved in NEB-oriented initiatives, such as [NEB Goes South](#), the [New European Bauhaus of the Mountains](#), [Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus](#), the [Friends of NEB](#), the [NEB High Level Round Table](#), and NEB Labs across all of the EU cities and regions, leveraging the already extensive networks within those frameworks. Cooperation with these initiatives includes the organisation of co-creation events that lead to high-level recommendations for developing the Deployment Roadmap. The work undertaken by these initiatives can also be showcased as a success story on the NEB Observatory.

A synergy with the Nordic Bauhaus was already envisaged in November 2022: Nordic Bauhaus ran an event called *Bauhaus Goes To The Woods*² on 24 November 2022 that drew in wood producers, forestry and primary industry, environmental scientists, open data specialists, ministers and policymakers in countries for whom wood production is extremely important, as well as architects and construction firms with a particular interest in wood construction. By organising around topics of interest rather than industry specialism, the event was able to be much more inclusive. **DigiNEB will use thematic and mission-driven approaches to gather multidisciplinary communities that converge around specific shared missions.** Rather than simply gathering the members of the textiles industry, a textiles theme draws in various stakeholders interested in that domain that may not have been considered otherwise or who use textiles in a range of different applications – such as the aeronautics industry. By organising engagement channels around missions and topics such as textiles, DigiNEB can more closely align with the NEB principles of openness, inclusion and multidisciplinary.

Lists, such as the one above, are unavoidably exclusive, so DigiNEB focuses on open, inclusive targets that include existing NEB initiatives such as *Nordic Bauhaus*, the community-led NEB Lab project *Carbon Free Bauhaus*, *Bauhaus Goes South* and their stakeholder groups. DigiNEB has on its External Advisory Board (EAG) Matti Kuittinen, a representative of the Finnish Ministry of the Environment and Chair of the Nordic Bauhaus, and Professor José Pedro Sousa of *Bauhaus Goes South*, both of which have extensive networks of their own.

² <https://www.nordicbauhaus.eu/into-the-woods#/page=1>

In addition, the DigiNEB consortium aims to establish synergies with projects that operate in the local living spaces and digital environments, such as:

- [AURORAL](#): Architecture for Unified Regional and Open digital ecosystems for Smart Communities and Rural Areas Large scale applications.
- [DUET](#): Virtual city replicas that make it easy to understand the complex interrelation between traffic, air quality, noise and other urban factors. Powerful analytics model the expected impacts of potential change to aid evidence-based operational decisions and longer-term policy choices.
- [CommunityCity](#): A transformative citizen-centred project that is launching 100 tech pilots addressing the needs of cities and communities through co-creation and co-learning processes.
- [CrAft](#): Part of the New European Bauhaus initiative that places the transition to climate neutrality at the heart of urban stakeholders. The project supports the Mission Board on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and the NetZeroCities platform in designing and deploying Climate City Contracts based on knowledge from CrAft's 3 Sandbox Cities (Bologna, Prague, and Amsterdam) and 60 CrAft Reference Cities.

Connections with these projects have been established through 3rd-party events joined by the DigiNEB team (Barcelona Smart City Expo and OASC Connected Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities Conference). The cooperation spans from organising events to sharing digital solutions that are added to the Digital Toolkit of success stories in the Observatory. All of these projects have been engaged and onboarded during the CERN event during the first part of the project.

7.4. Multipliers

The Multiplier network is showcased in Annex 1 Stakeholder groups and multiplier network.

Chapter 2 above lists highly relevant initiatives that are exploited to multiply the effects of the engagement process with the final aim of creating a comprehensive network facilitating interactions between digital and NEB players.

UPDATE: Through the JUST Industry Data Week, the project is connecting to industry, European Digital Innovation Hubs (Linköping Science Park), the EU Capital of Innovation (Linköping, Sweden), and Digital Projects as per the DOA.

Engagement with data ethics and AI for social good has emerged as a significant area of focus within the DigiNEB project, especially in alignment with the *JUST Industry Data Week* event. Over the first 18 months of the project, it has become clear that the intersection between ICT and NEB communities must prioritise ethical considerations in data management and the application of AI technologies for societal benefit.

This shift in focus represents a renewed engagement strategy, one that places data ethics and AI for social good at the heart of DigiNEB's overarching plan. Our multiplier activities have increasingly centred around these themes, driving collaboration with a wide range of projects that explore ethical data management, AI-driven solutions for public good, and prototyping NEB concepts with ICT innovations. These efforts underscore DigiNEB's commitment to advancing responsible, inclusive technological solutions in line with NEB principles.

8. Monitoring

The impact of all strategically important DigiNEB activities performed is measured through a core set of key performance indicators (KPIs) wherever they are quantifiable. Continuous monitoring activity is carried out by the T4.3 task leader and shared with all partners.

8.1. KPIs

Qualitative metrics come into play whenever there is a need for a deeper analysis of the relevance of outcomes achieved. The table below shows the end-of-project KPI targets and their status at M24.

KPI Number	Description	Status at M24	KPI objective at M27
1	F2F General Meetings	5	5
2	EAB members engaged	17	10
3	EAB strategic meetings	4	2
4	Digital solutions mapped and part of the DigiNEB Toolkit	138	250
5	Open licenses (e.g. MIT) with existing projects	50	25
6	TWGs	4	4
7	Projects/initiatives in the Observatory	168	500
8	Policy briefs by TWGs	1	4
9	Gap & Landscape Analysis report	1*	1
10	Unique visitors to DigiNEB (monthly)	7.88K	10K
11	Website Iteration	3	3
12	Early Adopters	13	100
13	Synergies created	70	100
14	Stakeholder database (incl social media)	594	3000
15	Newsletters including info from DigiNEB	12	21
16	Users engaged at events	1800	2000
17	Videos	16	24
18	Social media content items published on socials (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	97	192
19	Social media followers (total all channels)	980	7000
20	Visualisation of videos (cumulative)	1985	120000
21	Webinars organised (100 attendees each)	6	8
22	Workshops organised (50 attendees each)	8	16
23	Yearly events organised (150 attendees each)	1	2
24	NEB Roadmap	1*	1
25	Marketing Campaigns	4	6
26	Attended external events	42	not set

* Preliminary versions

Table 7 - DigiNEB KPIs

8.2. Website monitoring

All website analytical data is gathered continuously using **Cloudflare Analytics** to derive detailed statistics about online engagement. Monitoring will be in place to track the project KPIs related to website performance, proactively detect possible problems, and implement corrective actions. The Google Analytics profile was set up in M1, and the first data about traffic sources, visitors, navigation

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paths and conversions are being tracked. The primary data will be disclosed in the upcoming dissemination deliverables. Dynamic engagement strategies will respond to real-time online metrics. Project update reports will be collected as a more statistically significant data source as traffic grows due to upcoming communication and engagement activities.

A traffic KPI has been set for the activities in WP4 that will be measured with Cloudflare Analytics:

- Traffic: # sessions per month >1.5k at M12, >5k at M24;

The traffic KPI (# of sessions) will be pursued with close cooperation with the communication activities in WP5. As an example of such collaboration, a set of different copy templates for social media posts can be tested to assess which format is more attractive, thus resulting in more traffic.

Other relevant metrics, even if not set as KPIs, will be monitored to assess the success of the operation: individual logins, session duration, number and frequency of new vs returning users, conversion actions (e.g., submitting a web form or downloading a pdf), etc. These, in turn, will help achieve the communication target KPI by helping the communication teams focus on activities that are not only designed to increase traffic but also ensure social media visits.

Similarly, traffic sources, visitor geographies, most viewed pages, etc., are breakdown dimensions that will help us understand which parts of the NEB digital hub are being actively visited and which are not in terms of traffic acquisition and content generation.

A customised dashboard depicting our Cloudflare Analytics results has been set up to monitor these breakdown dimensions and will be updated monthly until M24 (September 2024). In the snapshot below, examples of such metrics and dimensions are shown:

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Fig.9 Snapshot of DigiNEB Cloudflare Analytics

Future versions of the dashboard include and monitor variables such as the adoption of digital tools and all other relevant KPIs identified by all WPs. The adoption growth will be marked in a

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benchmarking activity assessing hands-on engagement and adoption of digital tools in a blended environment that will include technology providers.

User feedback will be collected, and all input will be processed and reverted to the various WPs for iteration and channelling towards further deployment and benchmarking activities. Finally, the successful deployment of technologies will be assessed in a series of feedback loops.

8.3. Other impact monitoring

Throughout the DigiNEB lifecycle, the project team is going to evaluate the impact of all the engagement activities performed:

Engagement Activity	Description	Impact by M03
Organisation of webinars, workshops, yearly events and participation in 3rd-party events	The organisation and participation in events help DigiNEB give visibility to the NEB Digital Ecosystem to all identified SG categories.	The project has reached 149 stakeholders through the webinar and 10,000+ people through third-party events
Development of the Community Database	The Community Database collects all stakeholders DigiNEB has engaged with through social media channels, newsletters or online and physical events.	594 people (362 are coming from social media)
Establishment of Digital Focus Groups	The Digital Focus Groups bring together top-class experts of the NEB digital ecosystem to stimulate discussions and share best practices that are collected to provide strategic policy recommendations.	The identification of the TWGs experts is in progress, and their work will generate four landscape reports and contributions to the two iterations of the DigiNEB Roadmap
Establishment of synergies	Establishment of strong synergies with initiatives in the NEB and local living spaces area to foster the adoption of digitalisation to build more inclusive, sustainable and beautiful living spaces.	The dialogue to clarify the scope of collaboration has started with nine synergies
Development of the Digital Toolkit	The NEB Digital Toolkit comprises digital tools developed by technology providers and EC-funded projects.	27 Digital Solutions added.
Development of the Observatory	The Observatory maps and disseminates the projects and activities in the NEB landscape with a particular focus on R&I projects. It comprises success stories, TWG discussions, and Early Adopters' stories and events.	15 items added, of which: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 success stories - 4 TWG discussion groups - 8 events
Development of the eLearning catalogue	Collaborative online catalogue of initiatives and digital solutions that include best practices and training materials. The eLearning courses stimulate knowledge sharing and are freely accessible on the DigiNEB platform.	The impact by M03 cannot be evaluated as the activity will start in M06. The eLearning catalogue aims to reach 1000+ trainees

Table 8 - Impact monitoring

9. Risks and Mitigations

The following table identifies risks identified during the first months of WP4 implementation and the corresponding risk-mitigation measures implemented so far. Risks with high severity have been mitigated a-priori. All risks - both those already-identified and potential new ones - are being continuously monitored at project runtime. New risks/mitigation measures arising from engagement activities are managed as part of **Subtask 1.1.3 Risk management, ethics and IPR management**.

Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
R1	Lack of liaisons with pan-European & National initiatives Likelihood: Low Impact: High	Consortium members are exploiting established links with all major EC-recognised initiatives in Europe and globally: NEB, NEBC16, EIT, EIC, EOSC, ECTP (the European Construction and Technology Platform), CoR, Interreg, Covenant of the Mayors, EU Capitals of Culture, EU Green Capitals, EU Capitals of Innovation, EU Women Innovators, and more. Also, familiarity with and ease of access to the EC’s DG CONNECT actors and projects (including close involvement with several “booster” initiatives: Horizon Results Booster, HSbooster.eu) is currently being leveraged to find relevant synergies for DigiNEB’s community (e.g. early adopters, the External Advisory Board, thematic working-group members). Participation in key events such as the Barcelona Smart Cities World Expo Congress and the OASC Connected Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities Conference has strengthened pan-European liaisons. Should difficulties arise in the project’s next stages, activation of “Task Forces” will be sought, with win-win value propositions. Finally, concertation efforts will be initiated involving key stakeholders.
R2	Lack of engagement from relevant stakeholders Probability: Medium Impact: Medium	With their influential network and pan-European standing, all partners are committed to inherently mitigating the risk of lack of interest from target audiences. During the first months, DigiNEB has created meaningful relations to integrate with the NEB movement, creating a shared communication strategy. Moreover, it has also adopted and implemented a stakeholder management framework designed according to agile principles. Such an approach implies periodically assessing whether its approach is sufficiently inclusive and if the adequate target audience or candidates have shifted (also based on the feedback gathered from interacting with them). In the following months, DigiNEB will reinforce its efforts to attract the most challenging regional stakeholders, including the use of powerful networks and resources of partnering organisations such as strong alliances with the Committee of the Regions and Interreg Europe, all EU communication channels, and those that DigiNEB is synergising within the digital and industrial domains. Proactive use of communication channels by all partner networks will be engaged to inform about the breakthrough uses of technologies and stimulate widespread adoption.
R3	Capacity building and tech transfer difficulties Probability: Low Impact: High	To mitigate risks of insufficient technological knowhow, capacity building effectiveness, and tech transfer bottlenecks, DigiNEB is engaging experienced facilitators (e.g. External Advisory Board , Early Adopters) and using well-established tested methodologies for rapid upskilling with novel technologies, such as those developed by partners TU Delft and ICF. ³

³ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00207543.2021.1989514>

Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
		Through its open innovation platform, DigiNEB is fostering inclusive co-creation and exploitation of all NEB results in the wider business community (e.g. architects, designers, construction, creative sector, social actors), dedicated outputs for higher education and VET (see the success stories published so far in the observatory and the digital solutions included in the NEB Digital Toolkit).
R4	Lack of interoperability Probability: Low Impact: Low	Risks associated with the engagement of stakeholders include the establishment or replication of non-interoperable systems. This is not simply a technical problem of data, but a cultural and engagement problem often encountered when working with multidisciplinary communities with digital assets and data sets built within different systems to meet sector-specific standards. This may lead to the exclusion of large sections of potential stakeholders. As a mitigation strategy, the DigiNEB consortium ensures interoperability and ontology harmonisation across domains by sharing know-how from projects such as OntoCommons, a CSA dedicated to the standardisation of data documentation through harmonisation, standardisation and coordination, particularly in the realm of materials and manufacturing. Lessons and strategies from OntoCommons will inform DigiNEB approaches to stakeholder data.
R5	Being perceived as a fringe initiative Probability: Low Impact: Medium	Another risk identified by consortium partners is being seen as fringe or alternative and, therefore, not core to missions. As this is primarily an issue of communication and dissemination, DigiNEB is currently the key digital vehicle for engagement, learning, funding information and mapping overview across all programmes connected with NEB. An example is the promotion of the NEB academy, which will be carried out during the project's duration.
R6	Separation into silos Probability: Low Impact: Medium	The creation or reinforcement of existing silos within the wider digital and NEB communities provides a potential risk where different specialisms or groups within that community do not speak to each other, thereby preventing potential synergies and multidisciplinary possibilities and excluding those who may be made to feel they do not belong. Adopting thematic and mission-oriented approaches (e.g. thematic working groups, local workshops) provides an effective mitigation strategy, allowing for inclusion through interest rather than membership in a particular silo or specialism.
R7	Exclusion due to low digital skills Probability: Low Impact: High	Those with fewer digital skills or lower levels of digital access are at risk of exclusion. Providing introductory training in free, open-source tools that allow full participation will address this significant barrier for some valued community members. Examples include eLearning courses and other sector-specific training initiatives that will be organised according to specific needs. Additionally, using Thematic Working Groups instead of only Technical WGs can help reduce the risk of exclusion.
R8	Lack of evidence of co-creation Probability: Low Impact: Low	As it is vital for the DigiNEB project to align with NEB principles, the website and digital platform format allow effective contributions based on co-creation and not simply the delivery of results. Rather than act as a broadcast platform where the project announces its successes, the DigiNEB website constitutes a dynamic environment, with spaces dedicated to discussions and a user-friendly platform allowing individual contributions through a cost-free subscription. While live moderation can be resource-intensive, it acts as an effective form of online engagement when implemented in conjunction with the activity of Thematic and Technical Working Groups.

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Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
R9	Lack of incentive for participation Probability: Low Impact: High	In the co-creation of this engagement strategy plan, consortium partners identified a potential lack of incentive for participation. Risk mitigation strategies include using analytics and setting KPIs (either established in advance or developing live as a series of dynamic goals and indicators), developing new feedback mechanisms, and creating and disseminating tangible success stories (see DigiNEB observatory). The use of these measures allows for the demonstration of the effect of co-creation on engagement.

Table 9 – Risks and mitigations

Future risk scenarios that might arise during the execution will be notified to the Technical Project Coordinator (see Grant Agreement Section 2.3.4.1) in order to co-devise a mitigation plan to review the project objectives and detail a contingency plan to minimise the impact of the risk.

10. Conclusions

This deliverable outlines the foundational elements of DigiNEB’s evolving stakeholder engagement strategy, expanding on the actions necessary to achieve the project’s ambitious goals and incorporating new tools and methodologies that have emerged since the original plan. The key developments covered in this deliverable include:

- The DigiNEB community will continue to be engaged through both targeted and thematic approaches. While the project initially focused on the 7 distinct Stakeholder Groups (SGs), it has become clear that a mission-driven, interdisciplinary approach allows for greater fluidity between sectors. Stakeholders are now more likely to self-select based on their interests, bridging previously distinct professional and industry boundaries, and expanding the reach of NEB principles to new sectors and areas of focus, such as AI ethics.
- A diversity of channels will be leveraged to engage stakeholders, including an increased focus on an upgraded website, and enduring content such as the *NEB Concepts* podcast and the *Handbook for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation*. These channels are designed to foster learning, collaboration, and knowledge-sharing within the community. Additionally, early adopters, digital focus groups, and NEB’s existing networks will continue to play a crucial role in driving engagement.
- The document outlines a comprehensive plan of action that coordinates all engagement activities and clarifies the areas where support from project partners is expected. These activities will be aligned with the project’s evolving strategic focus, particularly around key themes like data ethics and AI for social good.
- Monitoring tools and activities have been updated to reflect the introduction of new digital platforms, such as the revamped website, and new engagement metrics from podcasts, hybrid events, and the NEB Observatory. These will ensure that the project’s dynamic engagement strategy responds effectively to real-time feedback and data, making it more adaptable to stakeholder needs.
- Relevant engagement risks and mitigation actions have been considered, particularly in light of the expanded scope of the project. These include managing the fluidity between stakeholder groups, ensuring regional engagement through the handbook, and adapting to the evolving interdisciplinary focus.

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This document, *D4.2*, represents the updated version of the *Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption & Monitoring Report*, building on the foundation of *D4.1* and refining the project's approach based on the progress, observations and reflections made during the first 18 months. It will continue to be updated in the final deliverable *D4.3*, ensuring that DigiNEB remains responsive to the evolving needs of its community and stakeholders.

11. References

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● Annex 1: Stakeholder groups and multiplier network

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Value proposition	Description	Multipliers
SG1	Architects, Designers, Engineers, and other professionals belonging to the NEB community	Support the identification of needs, gaps and requirements for the implementation of the NEB initiative, and contribute to NEB digitisation through the adoption of innovative, cutting-edge solutions, which will be displayed in the NEB digital toolkit and popularised by Thematic Working Groups and success stories.	Designers of buildings who adopt innovative digital solutions that contribute to bringing digitalisation to the New European Bauhaus. Creators of construction drawings who use NEB digital solutions to improve the quality of their pieces of work.	Official NEB partners, Architects’ Council of Europe, Architectural Research European Network Association, Alliance for Solar Mobility, Culture Action Europe, Cumulus Association, Europa Nostra, Future Architecture platform, European Council of Engineers Chambers, European Council of Interior Architects, European Council of Spatial Planners, Local Governments for Sustainability, the European Region of the International Federation of Landscape Architects, Trans Europe Halles, German Academy for Urban and Regional Spatial Planning, Swiss Society of Engineers and Architects, FNCAUE, AACHEN BUILDING EXPERTS e.V. – ABE; ADC*E: Art Directors Club of Europe; AECEF – Association of European Civil Engineering Faculties; EU National Institutes for Culture (EUNIC); European Environmental Bureau; European Network of Cultural Centres, World Crafts Council Europe, New European Bauhaus’ Friendship Group, NEB High Level Round Table, NEB Lab, International Federation of Landscape Architects, NEB Festival, Eurocities, European Network of Living Labs, European Fashion Heritage Association, Architects’ Council of Europe (ACE), Architectural Research European Network Association (ARENA), Alliance for Solar Mobility (ASOM), Culture Action Europe (CAE), Cumulus Association, Europa Nostra, Future Architecture platform, European Council of Engineers Chambers (ECEC), European Council of Interior Architects (ECIA), European Council of Spatial Planners (ECTP), ELIA, ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability, IFLA Europe (European Region of the International Federation of Landscape Architects), Trans Europe Halles (TEH), German Academy for Urban and Regional Spatial Planning (DASL), Swiss Society of Engineers and Architects (SIA), FNCAUE, ENCORD European Network of Construction Companies for Research and Development.
SG2	Construction industry suppliers & other relevant industry players, including start-ups, SMEs,	Support organisations with an appetite for gaining a role in the NEB arena and foster NEB-related innovation facilitating cross-industry interactions among start-ups and SMEs in sectors such as	Construction engineers who benefit from adopting NEB digital solutions to optimise building environments. Building organisations	European Construction, Built environment and Energy efficient Building Technology Platform (ECTP), World Green Buildings Council (WGBC), FIEC European Construction Industry Association (EU), Coalition for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings Europe (CEEB Europe), Forest-based Sector Technology Platform (FTP), Fire Safe Europe (FSEU), EOS European Organisation of the Sawmill Industry (EU), EPF European Panel Federation (EU), CEI-Bois European Woodworking Industry Confederation (EU), EFBWW European Federation of Building and Woodworkers (EU), EURADA European Association of Development Agencies* (EU), SSG Slovenski Gradbeni Grozd (Construction Cluster of Slovenia) (SI), UITP – The international association for public transport, MOVE EU, AVERE – the European Association for Electromobility, EIT Community Booster, European Digital SME Alliance, Enterprise Europe Network, StartUp Europe Partnership, Small Business Magazine, Essential Review – Europe Startup News, European Startup

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	associations in the building, mobility & health sectors, and SDOs	mobility, planning and health.	that foster NEB-related innovation facilitating cross-industry interaction.	Association, Startup Europe Regions Network (SERN), Startup Europe Partnership (SEP), EU Startup Monitor, SMEUnited, SME Europe, European Small Business Alliance (ESBA), Small Business Standards (SBS), European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA), EBN (European Business and Innovation Centre Network), European Association of Craft and SMEs (UEAPME), EUROCHAMBRES, UNIFE- The Association of the European Rail Industry, AER- Association of European Radios, PGEU- Pharmaceutical Group of the European Union, ENTSO-E European Network of Transmission System Operators, EUROPEN- European Organization for Packaging and the Environment, Built Environment Commons (FR), ACCIONIA (ES), ARUP (UK), Bouygues Construction (FR), EDF (FR), FCC (ES), STRABAG (DE), Uponor (FI), Focchi (IT), Mostostal (PL), CSBT (FR), Fraunhofer BIA (DE), RISE (SE), , TNO Built Environment (NL), VTT (FI), AITT (AT), BBRI (BE), Nobatek (FR), CNR-ISA (IT), FEUP (PT), TUM (DE), UPM Kymene Corporation* (FI), Business Joensuu (FI), Steinbeis entrumEuropa (DE), EURAC (IT), UNINOVA (PT), R2M Solution (IT), ETSI, Cen-Cenelec, oneM2M, HL7, IEEE, IEEE Cloud Computing, IEEE Future Networks, IEEE Smart Cities, iIRDS, ISO, IEC, ITU, IETF, OASIS, UN/CEFACT, W3C, CRSI – Concrete Reinforcing Steel Institute, Sheet Metal and Air Conditioning Contractors’ National Association (SMACNA), AES – Audio Engineering Society, CIE – International Commission on Illumination, IATA – International Air Transport Association, IUPAC – International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, NEMA – National Electrical Manufacturers Association, NIBSC – National Institute for Biological Standards and Control, IEA – International Energy Agency, NFPA – National Fire Protection Association, International Association of Oil & Gas Producers (IOGP), IATA – International Air Transport Association, IUPAC – International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, NEMA – National Electrical Manufacturers Association, Bauhaus Construction LTD, European Confederation of Woodworking Industries (CEI-Bois), European Panel Federation (EPF), European Federation of Building and Woodworkers (EFBWW), European Factory Platform, European Factories of the Future, FoodDrinkEurope, European Federation of Associations of Health Product Manufacturers (EHPM), Shift2Rail, FNTP Fédération Nationale des Travaux Publics (FR), IVL (SE), BAM (DE), IERC (IE), StoraEnso (SE), SLC – Standards Leadership Council, United Nations Forum on Sustainability Standards (UNFSS), FairTrade International, ISO/TC 130 Graphic technology, ISO/TC 59/SC 13 Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM), ISO/TC 38 Textiles, ISO/TC 89 Wood-based panels, ISO/TC 215 Health informatics, ISO/TC 268 Sustainable cities and communities, ISO/TC 287 Sustainable processes for wood and wood-based products, AFNOR, ASRO, Austrian Standards, BSI, DIN, DPS, ILNAS, IPQ, ISBIH, IST, LST, LVS, NBN, NEN, NSAI, PKN, SFS, SIS, SIST, Standard Norge, UNE, UNI.
SG3	Research and academia	Proactively find stimuli for new research and publications by favouring the sharing	Scientists that educate the next generation of leaders in NEB	European PPPs and Project Consortia – European Partnership for Key Digital Technologies, Processes4Planet – Transforming the European Process Industry for a sustainable society, People-centric sustainable built environment (Built4People), specific Horizon projects related to building/construction/urban transformation (e.g. BuildInWood, Basajaun). Past, ongoing and upcoming

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		of knowledge and learning, educating the next generation of leaders in the NEB digital domains.	and digital domains by sharing knowledge.	H2020 & HE Research projects & related outcomes, including the NEB lighthouse demonstrators, DIGITbrain, Rubizmo, CityZen, RURITAGE, UNISECO, BLUEfasma, OASIS, NextGen Micro cities, Integr@tención, mySMARTLife, e-MOPOLI, BIG HIT, EPIU GETAFE, INCIRCLE'S MISSION, CIVITAS DESTINATIONS, AURORAL, dRural, SmartX – The European Smart Textiles Accelerator, RE-DWELL, MobiliseSME, Wood4Bauhaus, DigiPlace, – European Partnership for Key Digital Technologies (KDT), Processes4Planet – Transforming the European Process Industry for a sustainable society, People-centric sustainable built environment (Built4People), NEB lighthouse demonstrators, European Digital Innovation Hubs – EDIH such as AIR4S – Artificial Intelligence & Robotics for Sustainable Development Goals, Application Center for Automation in Healthcare, ASSIST4SME – Digital Transformation of SME through Assistive Systems in Production, ASTURIAS DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB, Belgian Building Research Institute (BBRI), Brussels Creative, CETMA – Technologies Design and Materials European Research Centre, Cluster ICT, media and creative industries Berlin-Brandenburg, Cluster of Sustainable Building of Andalusia, Connected Mobility Hub, CONNECT5, Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (DASAI), DIGIS3 – Smart, Sustainable and Cohesive Digitalization, DigIT Hub Sweden, Digital Health-Biosciences (DIH-bio), Digital Innovation Hub for Society (DIH4S), Digital Innovation Hub for 3D printing (3DJPU), DIH for digital twins of logistics systems and manufacturing processes and systems (DIH_DiTMaPS), Good Life for Finland, GreenSupplyChain DIH, HPC-Cloud and Cognitive Systems for Smart Manufacturing processes, Robotics and Logistics, Living Lab for Smart Society (LL4SS), Plastipolis, Smart Connected Supplier Network, SmartCityTech, Research Association (EFFRA), European Factory Platform, European Factories of the Future Enterprise Europe Network, Architectural Research Network (ARENA), European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN), DIHNET.EU project.
SG 4	Digital technology companies & associations	Support the uptake of digital solutions and services relevant to the NEB initiative while creating a competitive advantage by testing and implementing new digital solutions and services.	Tech ecosystem that supports the uptake of digital solutions relevant to the NEB initiative through testing and implementing new digital services.	Blockchain Observatory Forum, IT Security Portal, TechNative, TechNativeLive, CloudPro, Tech Radar, IEEE IoT Journal, Artificial Intelligence Top News, ITProPortal, Net Technologies, Digital Twin Hub, Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation, Big Data Value AssociationEuropean Federation of Food Science and Technology (EFFoST), The European Technologies Industries (Orgalim aisbl), AI4EU, CISPE Cloud, CyberSec EU, Digital EU, ECSO, EIT Climate, EIT Digital, EIT InnoEnergy, Horizon Cloud Forum, INATBA, EIT, OFE – Open Forum Europe, Quantum Flagship, TNO, AIOTI, CEINNMAT (ES), TECNALIA Foundation (ES), DTI (DK), SINTEF (NO), EMPA (CH), 5G ACIA, ATIS (Alliance for Telecommunications Industry Solutions), DIGITAL EUROPE, TechNative, TechNativeLive, CloudPro, The Register, ITProPortal, SourceSecurity.com, IT Security Portal, Tech Radar, Net Technologies, European AI Alliance, IEEE IoT Journal, IEEE Communications Society, Research Europe, TCT Magazine, Artificial Intelligence Top News, Telensa, Inputech, Tech Nation, ACD Group, AEG ID, Asygn, AXEM Technology, Lab ID, Thales DIS BPS, ARGO Vision, Unify, SmartBot Parking, SMEunited, EIT Digital, Digital SME Alliance.

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<p>SG 5</p>	<p>Policy Makers, including Green Deal-related</p>	<p>Contribute to bridging EU policies and industry activities, supporting the design of policies at the intersection between NEB actors and digital players, and facilitating the future deployment of NEB initiatives.</p>	<p>European authorities that support the design and implementation of European policies at the intersection between NEB actors and digital players.</p>	<p>Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group (OISPG), The European Environmental Bureau, European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, European Environment Information and Observation Network, European Environment Agency, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), CEA (FR), GHG Protocol, ECOS, Carbon Trust, Green IT. Also, the European Commission - DG CONNECT, DG GROW, DG DIGIT, DG JRC, DG CLIMA, DG ECFIN, DG ENER, DG ENV, DG MOVE, DG REGIO, DG RTD, EU Environment.</p>
<p>SG 6</p>	<p>National & regional authorities, mayors (including urban planners) and cities</p>	<p>Upskill in the digital domain to improve cities' liveability, boost efficiency and effectiveness in project management, and facilitate the transformation of research results into concrete initiatives at the local level.</p>	<p>Regional and National authorities that support the design and implementation of local policies at the intersection between NEB actors and digital players.</p>	<p>NEB Lighthouses, all EU Capitals of Culture, all EU Green Capitals, all EU Capitals of Innovation, Members of the Covenant of the Mayors, ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability, Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR), Local Governments and Municipal Authorities Constituency (LGMA), European Federation Local Authority Chief Executive Officers, United Cities and Local Governments (UCLG), Global Taskforce of Local and Regional Governments, the Urban Development Network, the Smart Cities Marketplace, the EU Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy, EUROCITIES, the Union for the Mediterranean, the City Science initiative, Cities Mission, Climate Adaptation Mission, the Urban Development Network, the Smart Cities Marketplace, the EU Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy, EUROCITIES, the Union for the Mediterranean, the City Science initiative; this SG includes also representatives from the Committee of the Regions, Interreg Europe, Regional Governments from across the EU Member States.</p>
<p>SG 7</p>	<p>Civil society organisations and citizens</p>	<p>Increase awareness of NEB, promoting the adoption of its values related to the importance of sustainability, inclusiveness and aesthetics in living spaces to achieve a better quality of life.</p>	<p>Promoters of the NEB values and its adoption in living spaces to achieve a better quality of life.</p>	<p>Cradle to Cradle NGO, S-COM SUSTAINABLE COMMUNICATION AISBL, Air Pollution & Climate Secretariat (AIRCLIM), Global Atmospheric Pollution Forum, European Federation for Transport and Environment T&E, Danish Ecological Council (DOR), Rethink Plastic, EUROPEN- European Organization for Packaging and the Environment, People-Centered Smart Cities, Civil Society Europe, European Foundation Centre, Civic Space Watch, Green10, Placemaking Western Balkans, DoCoMoMo International, Citizen Science Lab at Leiden University, EU-citizen.science platform, ECSA – European Citizen Science Association, The Great Transformation.</p>

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- [Annex 2: DigiNEB White Paper](#)

DigiNEB White Paper

on the future of NEB in Horizon Programmes

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○ Editor's note

This White Paper is written in response to the European Commission working paper 'First Reflections on Building Blocks for the Design of a Possible EU Mission on the New European Bauhaus'. The contributing authors are thought leaders from the DigiNEB community – the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus. They include members of the DigiNEB External Advisory Board and leaders of NEB Lighthouse projects. Representatives of this community first came together during the DigiNEB event NEB@CERN 27 February – 1 March 2023 and, in a series of workshops, started to develop a comprehensive vision for the development of the New European Bauhaus digital ecosystem. A productive meeting about the NEB Mission was organised by DigiNEB with representatives from the NEB unit at the JRC in Zagreb on the 20th and 21st of September, 2023. This White Paper starts by referring to the original vision by President von der Leyen and the Concept Paper by the NEB High Level Round Table (HLRT) and proceeds to the contributions of the listed authors.

We adopted a pluralistic approach to capturing the voices of the community, representing sometimes differing views, and most importantly, not cancelling each other out. Each EAB member or lighthouse leader who was asked to contribute was tasked with creating a 1-2 pager on their positioning in respect of the NEB Mission. Each positioning was added as a separate chapter. Contributors could work together or amplify each other's vision, by agreement with the authors. Aside from small edits, contributions are left intact demonstrating a multiplicity of views and diversity of approaches. All are valid, and seldom contradictory. We have at times suggested more effective wording to convey the message, but we have allowed for a democratic representation of all the core voices from the community.

○ Framing the NEB vision

When President von der Leyen launched the New European Bauhaus in her inaugural State of the Union speech on the 16th of September 2020, it was the first time that she called for a *"co-creation space where architects, artists, students, engineers, designers work together"*. This call to create a multidisciplinary movement for co-creation is significant because, for the first time, she called for **translation of thought into practice** through the **prototyping of tangible solutions** that could turn into **evidence-based policy**.

A group of practitioners were invited as the President's High Level Round Table to translate their practice into a Concept for the New European Bauhaus. The first HLRT activity identified a strong **"line of justice"** that cut through all foundational values. Mapping desired outcomes was united by a strong concept of **"learning by doing"**. Social justice and knowledge exchange through hands-on practice was, therefore, very much at the heart of the initiative from the start.

For the HLRT, it wasn't just a case of translating their practice into the concept; it was also about **demonstrating it hands-on**, with some extraordinary examples. When the Ukrainian war broke out, architect Shigeru Ban and the Polish HLRT representative Hubert Trammer were on the ground on the border with Ukraine while 2 million people were crossing over into Poland in the first two weeks of the conflict. They assembled the Voluntary Architects Network to teach them how to create privacy shelters for immigrant families housed inside large hangars and sports halls. This knowledge was passed on and spread from the Polish border with Ukraine to the Slovakian borders, where volunteers fitted more shelters.

Another extraordinary example is the work of Sheela Patel. She works with women's collectives in informal settlements. One billion people are living in informal settlements around the world, and yet research into dwellings seldom considers this as a priority challenge. Sheela runs a project called "Roof Over Our Heads", which teaches how to build resilient, low-carbon, affordable homes. She embodies the idea of a **"beyond-European perspective"** that the HLRT deemed extremely important. To reinforce this perspective, the HLRT onboarded three more extraordinary people: Francis Kéré, Pritzker Prize winner for architecture from Burkina Faso; Nigerian-born Emeke Ogbob, an artist based in Berlin, and Ugandan activist Hilda Nakabuye.

The HLRT Concept Paper advocated for **radical inclusion**, where we are not divided into categories, but instead, we are encouraged to **focus on where we converge**. When we bring all kinds of domains together, **we don't cancel each other out**, but we respect and admire all the different knowledge and cultures that are brought to the table.

It is important also to acknowledge that humans are part of nature, and that our interdependence with the living environment including other species matters also for the large

societal transformation., So from the beginning, the NEB HLRT promoted the idea of "**more-than-human ecosystems**".

In practice, we have challenged urban planning and traditional approaches to land and infrastructure management and looked at ways in which we can plan by including living ecosystems in a novel research topic called "**Ecosystem Living**". This requires research and innovation in situ, **to each region according to its needs**. The idea of **place-based learning** is an integral part of this process.

The Floating University in Berlin – one of the winners of this year's New European Bauhaus prizes and also of the Golden Lion at the Venice Biennale two years ago – very much captures this idea of place-based learning and multidisciplinary knowledge exchange, but also, very importantly, it captures the **new knowledge** that results from these methods. One of the biggest challenges for the NEB mission is to demonstrate that these methods are much-needed for a sustainable and equitable future and that they are **an exceptional way of generating new knowledge**.

○ **The digital ecosystem perspective**

■ **Culture and community-driven digital systems can turn neighbourhoods into giant testbeds for solutions to grand challenges.**

Fifteen years ago, it was assumed that the internet was all about distributing information and providing downloads. Soon, it became apparent that the real value lay with content creators and uploads - commonly referred to as participatory culture. The same paradigm shift is required for data-enabled spaces in neighbourhoods. Culture doesn't exist only in the nodes and synapses of distribution networks – it thrives in all of the spaces in-between where citizens act as co-creators of information based on social and cultural protocols, where technology becomes an important element of new locally grounded experiential aesthetics.

Cultural interaction is an essential component of data-driven systems in neighbourhoods. Communities are *the driving force* of the neighbourhood's digital content. Active engagement of communities with their digital infrastructure can result in innovative solutions for community living, the use of data-enabled environments as a collaborative interface with governments, and the emergence of new inclusive languages of interaction, novel behaviours and subcultures. Considering culture and community as the drivers of digital systems allows neighbourhoods to become giant testbeds for solutions to grand challenges.

■ **Community neighbourhood testbeds using NEB methods allow for R&I to capture knowledge from a unique blend of diverse perspectives.**

Unlike homogenous research, technology or industry focus groups, community neighbourhoods offer a unique blend of diverse perspectives for generating new knowledge. Community neighbourhoods are primarily trans-generational and require research considerations of the youngest and oldest beneficiaries for any solution. They frequently blend the experience of citizenship with the roles of employee and business owner, joining the private and public domain. As we transform these neighbourhoods into more inclusive and natural spaces, they also become places of experimentation that challenge the nature/culture divide and call for regenerative and nature-based approaches. In many neighbourhoods, vernacular knowledge can be combined with frontier technologies. Such opportunities also arise from other functions and infrastructures next to which these neighbourhoods and communities are located—ports, airports, industrial districts, technology hubs, etc. to name just some—that can have an impact on health and liveability in the neighbourhoods. Cross-cutting engagement among neighbourhoods across Europe can help address larger projects in a shared way.

Research results at the intersection of diverse perspectives can be published in recognised journals such as the CERN IdeaSquare Journal of Experimental Innovation[1]. Community neighbourhoods can become the testbeds for what Latour called “the rejection of the discrete binaries of human/nonhuman, digital/material, subject/object, nature/culture, private/public, and individual/collective” - meaning that the NEB ecosystem works towards considering and

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uniting all diverse dimensions and interactions of communities and life and the larger context in which they are located.

■ **Mission-oriented multidisciplinary research is more than best practice combined.**

Intelligent cooperation is a phenomenal strategic skill and the heart of civilised coexistence and cultural evolution. Research that joins knowledge from various disciplines using the methodologies from the NEB community does not merely combine best practice from various disciplines but results in much more than the sum of its parts – it generates new knowledge and technological breakthroughs. This means that it can provide fast responses to the urgent environmental challenges with a level of advancement required to create sustainable solutions for grand missions.

The impacts of these collaborations include novel research directions and innovation methods, rapid upskilling and behavioural change, and many more that have been identified by the European Commission in the recent comprehensive research, analysis and report by the Knowledge Valorisation Communities of Practice. The Codes of Practice for knowledge valorisation of industry-academia collaboration and citizen engagement will be published by the end of 2023^[2]. The Code of Practice for the knowledge valorisation of intellectual property assets recommends participation in open innovation platforms which offer opportunities of open precompetitive public-private partnerships for cross-sectoral collaborations and knowledge exchange^[3].

■ **Multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration allows for a greater understanding of societal value networks.**

Working across disciplines generates valuable knowledge for the growing field of cross-domain digital systems that are required to manage transitions towards sustainable economies. Cross-domain systems are necessary for the effective management of closed-loop material/product life cycles and related material/product passports that have to traverse multiple domains and affect diverse stakeholders. The NEB programme can partner with initiatives such as Materials Commons, launched by DG RTD and AMI, that aims to create a broad community of material science stakeholders^[4]. As part of these systems, multidisciplinary approaches by the NEB community can enable material use to be monitored and kept within the limits set by the Donut Economy Model. Cross-domain networks can reveal systemic risks and align on resilience strategies and systems for responsibility.

■ **The core NEB values implemented with communities on the ground must be reflected in our digital systems.**

For broader impacts, it is vital to learn how to join forces with other knowledge domains and bridge various modes of expression. To ensure that core societal values are embedded in cross-domain data-driven ecosystems, interoperability of data spaces needs to be supported by a series of enabling mechanisms, including systems of agreements (from international regulation to P2P contracts), systems of resilience (environmental sustainability and "Black

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Swan Event" resilience), systems of responsibility (Corporate Social Responsibility, Responsible AI, Ethics), and systems of beliefs (societal values, including handling of data biases, information sensitivity and provenance). Setting up enabling systems has major implications on how we extract value from collaboration. Integrating digital elements into physical spaces fundamentally alters the perception and experience of these places, presenting distinct ethical challenges. These emerging hybrid spaces are becoming as central to community interaction and discussion as social media platforms. In response to this, rather than adopting a top-down approach with stringent policies and regulations, it's more effective to integrate appropriate parameters within the digital systems themselves. This strategy guides behaviours through positive incentives and motivations, fostering a more organic and self-regulated environment.

■ **Non-routine cognitive skills from design practice can safeguard the social and ethical dimension of technology in industrial applications.**

Design contributes non-routine cognitive skills, which are essential for original and often breakthrough insights in environments supported by frontier technologies. Within research programmes, design-led prototyping environments therefore are best placed to lead experiments where the impact of frontier technologies – such as AI, deep learning, extended reality and brain-computer interfaces – can be tested in safe environments and challenges addressed before applications are deployed at scale. These experiments test the extent to which the technology enables or obstructs human agency, decision-making processes and accountability. In this sense, we see culture and design as safeguarding the social and ethical dimension of technology and alleviating risks for deployment of novel applications for industry.

■ **Quality of experience of the lived environment must be included in all digital and data-enabled interactions stimulating virtuosities.**

In NEB, aesthetics is equated with quality of experience. Currently, European funding programmes universally lack quality in digital user experience and interfaces for research and industry. Poor quality interfacing leads to greater divides: low digital literacy, exclusion of those who cannot work out how to navigate content, greater inequality in accessing information, loss of benefits or services, and damage to democratic processes. Successful interaction with digital systems improves accessibility but also increases affordances to innovate and develop virtuosities. Before the invention of the piano, there was no pianist virtuoso - the idea and the affordance didn't exist. This applies to all novel technologies we design: quality interaction creates novel affordances for communities and ecosystems alike. The NEB is uniquely well-placed to create a programme of excellence for interaction with our physical and virtual living environments.

■ **Using NEB methods to prototype solutions in direct collaboration with industry can help transition to an Industry 6.0: Ecosystemic.**

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Our ambitions towards greater industrial sustainability demand a fast paradigm and behavioural shift towards sustainable ecosystems - a transition from Industry 5.0: Human-Centric to Industry 6.0: Ecosystemic. With the urgent transition of all industry to data-driven systems, the pace of transition has been forced to speed up considerably. Experimentation with NEB communities points to some clear clues for best practice in system design and new interactions with frontier technologies – as valuable new knowledge for the industrial transition. Demonstrating results in direct collaboration with industry can contribute to evidence-based industrial policy and speed up the transition towards ecosystemic industrial strategies.

Ecosystem living can serve as a paradigm for research into beyond-human cohabitation and smart communities.

Ecosystem living is a way to reframe the concept of urban planning by questioning whether *urban* is a necessary (or even desirable) condition for human habitation. It transcends the idea of *spatial* planning since the focus of spatial planning is limited to the physical space and not the complex interactions between cohabiting species. It does not advocate for ecosystem *planning* because it does not seek to impose order, encourage extractive practices or create the conditions for entirely anthropocentric habitation. It considers human beings and their activities to be part of nature and not separate from it. True ecosystem living is about harmony, alignment and balance, and finding an entire value network within a holistic cohabitation. This balance must synthesise and integrate artistic practice, scientific research, traditional craft professions and local cultural practices. It follows that Smart Communities should, therefore, extend beyond human to the development of intelligent systems that can manage interdependencies of human and non-human natural ecosystems. This could be a path towards emphasising caring, nurturing, and contingency, enabling designers, architects, and engineers to think about systems as components of bigger assemblages and promote precarious flourishing over extinction.

Private partnerships can be incentivised by measuring the rate of community adoption of emerging market applications.

NEB communities operate at the heart of emerging cultures and subcultures. They are uniquely placed to participate in technology transfer to new and exciting cultural expressions and emerging market applications. Novel business models and new markets that emerge can be monitored through market adoption. Evaluation of market adoption can use Market Adoption Readiness Levels (MARLs), already adopted by the recommendations of the CONNECT Advisory Forum (CAF) from 2014 and quoted in industry literature^[5]. Based on evaluations, the NEB programme can support the scaling of excellence from the ground up in partnership with regional private and public funding. Design-led solutions for industry can be linked to private investments while culture-led R&I can be linked to philanthropy with better and structurally embedded financing for NGOs, CCS and entrepreneurial micro-companies.

■ Connecting the grassroots communities from the regions with high-level policy strengthens the position of regional governments.

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The periphery – the outlying European Regions – can now be considered the centre of where we face the biggest threats of climate change. For example, European coasts and the understanding of seas and oceans are at the forefront of water system change and key to creating ecosystem living. The NEB Programme has the opportunity to prioritise research by communities who are currently poorly represented in the R&I programmes, including those that face geographical, cultural or economic barriers. With knowledge of regional ecosystem framework conditions, activists and project initiators on the ground, micro-companies from the culture and creative sectors, and private philanthropists who care for the preservation of local traditions and democracies are all valuable contributors to the creation of new knowledge and can promote regional interests strengthening the position of their regional governments. As a movement that is a bastion of democracy, NEB can scale intelligence from the outlying European Regions to the centre, connecting it directly to high-level policy.

■ **Ensuring a critical perspective of the NEB would foster pluralistic visions of the future.**

A critical review of the Bauhaus and NEB's would avoid perpetuating oppressive structures and instead foster pluralistic visions for the future. With its significant legacy in design and education, the original Bauhaus school faced scrutiny for its exclusionary practices and Eurocentric approach. Eurocentric modernity, as a concept that positions Europe as the center of the world, has had far-reaching impacts beyond its borders, fostering a worldview of human separation from nature and consequent exploitation of the environment and non-European cultures. The NEB must consider these legacies, acknowledging pluralistic approaches and the true impact of technology on diverse populations, striving to move beyond the exploitative mental models of Eurocentric modernity/coloniality. The NEB, while citing the original Bauhaus as a foundational influence, must contend with contemporary global movements aiming to dismantle symbols of imperialism and oppression. Such examples are manifested in contemporary design movements such as participatory design, humble design, and the degrowth movement. The NEB's broad definitions of beauty, sustainability, and inclusiveness do not explicitly address power structures or the possibility of plural interpretations. Critics argue that this vagueness might reproduce the myth of universalism, where a monolithic view of Europe prevails over its inherent diversity. Furthermore, the NEB's documents hint at the problematic notion of better living through technology, suggesting that new creations universally improve life, which critics say overlooks the diversity of needs and contexts. There's also concern that the NEB's ambition to spread its principles globally could perpetuate colonial dynamics. A critical stance is called for to ensure the NEB does not reinforce colonial capitalism and instead commits to an inclusive approach that effectively addresses climate change and embraces pluralistic solutions.

- **Culture-driven R&I**
- **A Mission that aligns with and enhances the NEB Vision**

As noted in the opening paragraph of the Working Paper, a key element of the NEB vision is to “leverage the power of culture, art and creativity for the transition.” (p.1). In its current form, the Working Paper falls significantly short of demonstrating how this key element of the NEB vision will be integrated into the proposed Mission. However, we also note that there is a predominant focus on the competitiveness and innovation of the construction industry. We therefore ask for the proposed Mission to valorise the role of the arts, culture and creativity in helping us to (re)imagine a collective future that is inclusive, sustainable and beautiful. The vitality of Europe’s artistic, cultural and creative sectors and spaces of learning is paramount to the success of the necessary transition.

First and foremost, culture and participation in cultural activities are at the very heart of democracy, civic engagement and social cohesion, as evidenced in a recent independent report on Culture and Democracy (European Commission, 2023). Investing in culture has demonstrable positive correlations with civic engagement and democratic outcomes in communities across the EU. This is even more pressing at a time when the climate crisis risks further eroding trust in democracy, while also exacerbating inequalities.

Second, creativity is an essential ingredient of the competencies needed for a green transition. As recently highlighted in GreenComp: the European sustainability competence framework, creativity supports exploratory thinking, which in turn is a key competence in informing and envisioning sustainable futures and acting for sustainability (Joint Research Centre, 2022). Creativity is an essential component of future literacy, together with science and values for sustainability.

Third, culture has been shown to be an essential leverage to the localisation of international policy agendas, helping to build connections between shared visions, local actions and communities (United Cities and Local Governments, 2023). In fact, the cultural and creative industries are consistently arguing for recognition as a fourth pillar of sustainable development under the broad umbrella of the UN SDG’s (Voices of Culture. Brainstorming Report, 2020^[6])

Fourth, art and culture are critical in deepening our relationship with nature and more than human entities. They can help establish the key values that guide ecosystem living. This connection is not just physical but also deeply cultural, influencing our traditions, knowledge, and artistic expressions. By valuing and incorporating these elements into the mission, we can create more immersive and engaging experiences that resonate deeply with individuals and communities. This approach can help to cultivate a greater sense of responsibility and stewardship towards our environment, encouraging sustainable practices and fostering a profound respect for the natural world. Ultimately, integrating these cultural and artistic dimensions into the Horizon Europe mission will not only promote environmental sustainability but also enrich the collective European cultural heritage, strengthening our shared identity

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and vision for a future that is both sustainable and deeply rooted in our diverse cultural experiences.

It follows that the NEB's vision of a cultural movement needs a vibrant cultural and creative sector. The arts and creativity are central to our need to reimagine our built environment beyond business as usual, and for a fair and greener transition that is co-owned by all and that leaves no one behind.

○ A Mission that places the interconnection between citizens and the built, lived, and natural environments centre stage

We welcome the Working Paper's initial reflections on the challenges, objectives, initiatives, research areas and outcomes of the proposed NEB Mission. However, we also note that there is a predominant focus on the competitiveness and innovation of the construction industry. We therefore ask that the balance is redressed, in order to extend the focus to the intersection of citizens and their lived, natural and built environments. Moreover, many other industries are central to unlocking the potential for more circular and regenerative economies and neighbourhoods, for example the fashion industry, the food industry or health. A narrow focus on the construction industry precludes the NEB from achieving its full potential and engaging a variety of stakeholders and sectors in the transition.

First the working paper states that “the proposed NEB Mission acknowledges that the circularity and the revitalisation of the built environment are closely linked to the cultural dimension of places. In other words, the way we shape our environment as a whole is an expression of our culture, cultural heritage, identity and diversity.” (p.6). We find that this statement fails to acknowledge power differentials as well as intersectional inequalities and discrimination. Before benefits to the industry, the needed transition must have positive impacts for citizens, through fair and good employment opportunities, learning and education outcomes, and improvements to living conditions and public spaces and services.

We urge the proposed Mission to adopt a postcolonial lens, which problematizes dominant hierarchies in knowledge production and representation among others, in order to reimagine our built and lived environment for a fair and greener transition that leaves no one behind.

Second, the Mission must also reflect the complexities of built environment interventions on the lived and natural environment. Acting on the built environment is framed as a ‘silver bullet’ in our goal of climate restoration (p.4). Yet there are countless examples of interventions on the built environment that have broken communities and social and cultural ecosystems down. The Tweebosbuurt in Rotterdam is a case in point: the bulldozing and rebuilding of an entire neighbourhood may have made the built environment more sustainable, but it also wiped out community bonds and social capital due to displacement. The proposed mission must acknowledge that displacement and green gentrification are a real threat to our cities’ communities and cultures.

Third, we urge the proposed Mission to acknowledge true experimentation and social innovation beyond growth, markets and business models for industry competitiveness.

Finally, we agree that neighbourhoods are the scale at which interventions can impact most. But from our experience, we should also ensure that we do not treat neighbourhoods as laboratories where top-down innovations are implemented. At the same time, we also recognise the importance of having enabling frameworks, infrastructure and policy on city, and country level in order to be successful (and for people not to keep hitting barriers when they try to implement change or upscale their bottom-up projects). Co-ownership and co-design should be at the heart of the proposed Mission. Moreover, the shift in practices and

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mindsets is not just needed in the neighbourhoods but also in our institutions, ending the colonising attitude towards residents and acknowledging that the best solutions are ones where grassroots communities own the resources and can address the challenges collectively and collaboratively. We recommend that the implementation and further development of the mission keep alive the co-creative spirit that the NEB had in its initial phases involving many different stakeholders in the process and therefore getting stronger results.

Recommendations

Challenge	Objective	Intervention areas	Research Area	Outcomes
Challenge 1: Europe has set a major ambition to be a world leader in green transformation, <u>but how can this transformation be truly regenerative for people and planet?</u>	General objective: Foster a fair, sustainable transition for all, leveraging local cultures and creativity	Acknowledging the role of creativity as a key competence in sustainability transitions	Research alternative learning environments and forms of knowledge production	A transition to a fair, sustainable and beautiful future that leaves no one behind
Challenge 2: Climate change is accelerating, <u>and its impact is most hardly felt by those who experience multiple and intersectional forms of disadvantage and discrimination.</u> The pace of transformation remains too slow.		<p>Foster social innovations that and implement governance models that can balance public and private interests in green and fair transition.</p> <p>Provide tools, services and infrastructure for the common good – inclusive, affordable, safe and accessible for all.</p>	Applying an intersectional and postcolonial lens to climate change transition	

<p>Challenge 3: As climate change deepens existing social and territorial inequalities, it also risks eroding trust in democratic institutions</p>		<p>Invest in cultural infrastructure to help foster civic engagement, democratic participation and social cohesion</p> <p>Support a new set of standards for the development and transformation of living spaces that accounts for citizen ownership and participation.</p>		

Table 1: suggestions for a revised NEB Mission Intervention Logic (based on Joint Research Centre, 2023:11)

References:

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European Commission (2023). Culture and Democracy: the evidence. How citizens' participation in [cultural activities enhances civic engagement, democracy and social cohesion](#).

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Joint Research Centre, European Commission (2023). [First reflections on building blocks for the design on a possible EU Mission on the New European Bauhaus](#).

United Cities and Local Governments, Committee on Culture (2023). [Localising the SDGs with a Cultural Perspective. Initial results of the Seven Keys programme](#).

○ A Mission that is about participation and democratic principles

Learning from tradition combined with future-oriented guidelines to comply with climate protection and to create a liveable environment requires new approaches. A worsening climate crisis exacerbates social and political inequalities. NEB is about participation and democratic principles.

Recommendations

- With emphasis on the importance of participation, green transformation should be designed in a socially acceptable way, using examples (case studies).
- For realisable and adaptable CO₂-reductions in the built environment interdisciplinary experimentation coupled (in parts) with grassroots innovation is necessary. Only research on technical issues without also including the social / cultural component is not enough and will fail in realisation. See “Urban Site Development as Temporal Carbon Storage—A Case Study in Germany” as an example of a legitimate and valuable means for the creation of new knowledge (<https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/14/5827>).
- What we need is research through implementation projects, focused on transparent analysis and based on common knowledge of the individual local communities, and recognition that this is just as important as basic scientific research.
- The neighbourhood level as a mediating level is exactly the right starting point for implementation.
- It must become clear that much can be changed through culture and that this should definitely accompany quantitative research. Synergies from interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary work are immediately visible - a common sense can only emerge through this.
- In implementation, what is directly visible to people on the ground is important.

- A people-centred mission

- **Do we need a NEB Mission?**

The New European Bauhaus lighthouse project for Stavanger (NEB-STAR), with Utrecht and Prague as twinning cities, has now been in operation for one year. During this period, the project has made some discoveries and built up some experiences that influence how we see New European Bauhaus implementation. These discoveries and experiences stem from close contact with citizens, organizations, businesses, social entrepreneurs, coupled with close interaction with local, regional, and national authorities.

NEB-STAR addresses four emblematic challenges:

1. *Challenges linked to the use, preservation and reconversion of existing infrastructure and heritage:* Co-creating a new sense of aesthetics for climate-neutral cities and communities that captures places' unique qualities, history and potential, and generates a sense of belonging, pride and ownership;
2. *Environmental and climate adaptation challenges, environmental and climate risks, prevention and resilience:* Reconnecting with nature to boost resilience and a sense of community, giving new life to the spaces in between buildings through food and nature;
3. *Social challenges (poverty, segregation, social exclusion, etc.):* Creating temporary meeting spaces in urban transition areas, that embrace diversity and strengthen the identity and uniqueness of people and places that need it most;
4. *Economic and territorial changes linked to the green transition:* Co-creating co-benefits for the neighbourhood and city through multi-functional use of spaces and infrastructures

The four emblematic challenges addressed by NEB-STAR align with many of the five Missions that the European Commission has already identified. We can see direct and indirect links to work being done on climate neutrality and the adaptation to climate change, the restoration of our ocean and waters, and to the work being done to transition to more healthy soils. In NEB-STAR as well as the other NEB Lighthouses, we see that NEB is closely intertwined with the 5 Missions. These 5 Missions and the societal challenges they address already have extensive research and innovation programs that will fund innovation and push the transition in wanted directions.

- **NEB-STAR recommendation:**

- **Do not launch a new mission on the New European Bauhaus at this point in time.**

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- **Integrate NEB values and principles into the 5 Missions and their Mission Platforms first.**
- **Before launching a potential mission, the current NEB lighthouses should be evaluated.**

The NEB Lighthouse projects are excellent examples of such integration between NEB and the Missions. The way we read the JRC Working Document, it does not seem to build on the experience of the lighthouses and could even be seen to pull in a different direction.

Based on the experiences that the NEB-STAR project has built up during the first year, we recommend that the NEB Lighthouses as well as other projects funded within NEB and the Missions first get evaluated and important experiences and learnings extracted to inform further actions. First after this evaluation, the need for a separate NEB Mission can be assessed.

■ **In case of a NEB Mission**

In the European Commission's first reflections on building blocks of the design of a potential New European Bauhaus (NEB) Mission, it reiterates that "The EU missions are designed for addressing complex and interconnected issues" connected to larger societal challenges.

However, the core of the Joint Research Centre's (JRC) working paper seems to revolve much more narrowly and focused around the construction sector, mainly addressing the circular economy, industry, technology, and sustainable materials. This makes it:

- **Too focused on the ongoing renovation wave and construction.**
- **Too far removed from the overall European Green Deal.**
- **Too far removed from other missions and climate action.**

The JRC Working Document appears to give the impression that we can simply build our way out of climate change, when our experience and the science clearly shows this is not feasible.

NEB is intended to link the European Green Deal to our daily lives and living spaces, focusing on the values of sustainability, aesthetics and inclusion. While recognising the importance of the construction sector in promoting Europe's circular and regenerative initiatives, we believe there's more to consider than just focusing on residential buildings and their construction.

Several of the challenges addressed by NEB move beyond neighbourhoods (including circularity) - we would like to see both cities and rural communities addressed to a larger degree if a new mission is to be launched.

A NEB mission should, in our opinion, address whether anything new needs to be built and how other solutions can be developed and thus also promote a more systemic approach to the connection between spaces, people, nature, and the built environment. In short, focus on societal challenges and change.

Social and societal sustainability is currently lacking among the existing 5 Missions, which we believe is a critical aspect to include in a potential NEB Mission. This does not exclude the construction sector or a circular approach, quite the opposite.

Our society is facing a climate crisis, a nature crisis, but also a crisis of polarisation. It all begins with neighbourhoods/communities. This is where lives are lived. And where lives will be affected by the climate transition. However, we should be careful to narrow the mission to just future neighbourhoods, as it might overlook the interconnected nature of the challenges ahead as stated earlier. We should aim to rejuvenate not only neighbourhoods but also commercial areas, infrastructure, and cities at large. While the neighbourhood scale is undeniably significant, we shouldn't underestimate the forthcoming shifts and potential local concerns. Embracing participatory design on a broader scale is vital. In a circular economy (for example), various localities are interconnected through material flows, which could be a potential source of discord, especially among urban, rural, and peri-urban communities. Therefore, collaboration across different scales—from neighbourhoods to larger administrative regions and across administrative borders—is paramount.

A NEB mission with a too narrow focus on neighbourhoods / communities will not be able to fully demonstrate how the new, climate-neutral lives of the future will be lived. In addition, it will also fail to show in practice how the transition can be just, inclusive, and attractive to all, and in fact even improve our daily lives. This will be counter to the vision of a more sustainable future – for everyone.

A potential new NEB mission should be focused on people and collaboration and can thus serve as a catalyst for other missions. The mission should therefore ensure that the original intentions of NEB remain visible in the mission. This way, we can ensure a mission that truly is creative and transdisciplinary, bridging the world of science and technology, art and culture, and transforming our lives for the better through leveraging on the green and digital challenges. A NEB mission should seek to succeed in addressing complex societal problems through co-creation - which brings us back to what the missions are designed to do.

- **It is therefore our view, that we need:**
 - **A mission that focuses on people - the interaction between people, and the interaction between people, nature and the built environment.**

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- **A mission that sees people and their neighbourhoods as complex and interconnected spaces, where multiple activities and needs come together.**
 - **A mission that strengthens the feeling of inclusiveness and belonging for all in neighbourhoods/communities and can contribute to citizen empowerment.**
- **Radical Inclusion in R&I**

Solutions to tackle inequality and exclusion to support NEB's vision for tomorrow's neighbourhoods

The purpose of this section is to highlight the importance of accessibility, equality, and equity to raise the quality and sustainability of outcomes and joint projects to a new level, and to create opportunities for new perspectives on accessibility and equity.

The NEB Mission aims to revitalise European neighbourhoods with design for sustainability and inclusion. The mission will place inhabitants at the heart of the transformation, providing a horizon for democratic decision-making to tackle citizens' disconnect with implementing the green transition in their neighbourhoods. It will increase ownership and legitimacy and generate the scale needed to catalyse the green transformation in the construction industry, financing models, and on the ground.

The New European Bauhaus initiative is committed to accessibility and inclusion. To ensure that everyone feels safe and respected while participating in the initiative, it is essential to take into account the principles of safer space when working on NEB projects. The development of a New European Bauhaus approach, where all projects and events use the same accessibility mapping, and accessibility plans that describe how accessibility will be achieved in practice, and safer space principles, would have the potential to increase cohesion and transparency in neighbourhoods as well.

With these principles, all participants should have an equal opportunity to make their voices heard. It would bring the New European Bauhaus movement closer to the people and increase ownership, the sense that each of us is responsible for developing our community, preventing climate change, and fighting racism.

Safer space principles include respecting everyone's personal space, listening to others, respecting diversity, and using language that is respectful to all people. By taking these principles into account, NEB projects can be designed with accessibility in mind, ensuring that all buildings are accessible to people with disabilities, that all events are inclusive, and that all digital content and communication are accessible and respectful.

Encouraging participation from diverse communities in all aspects of the initiative is also important. This includes involving people from different cultures, genders, ages, and

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backgrounds in the design process. Providing training and resources to help partners and stakeholders create more accessible and inclusive spaces can also help achieve this goal. Partnering with organisations that specialise in accessibility and inclusion can ensure that best practices are being followed.

The introduction of accessibility and equality plans and safer space principles in the New European Bauhaus would be a strong example to all European actors of going all out for inclusion and equality and creating opportunities for all, regardless of cultural backgrounds or personal characteristics. No one is left out.

Checklists and guidelines could easily be added to the NEB website for all to use. Safer space principles for the NEB could be created between partners. In order to evaluate the impact of these tools on the working culture, tools on effectiveness are also needed. Making these policies become a natural part of the action will take time, but promoting equality and inclusion is an ongoing process, a long marathon, the results of which will also be visible in everyday encounters as awareness, knowledge, and understanding grows.

○ The New Bauhaus for global social justice

We now live in a world where all development investment has to acknowledge the reality that top down technology driven and exclusionary Northwest research has not produced the desired impact even with resources that have been spent in the last four decades. Whether it is the work of a “New Bauhaus” (as a global term) or it is any other form of investigation to find solutions for development that have a deep scientific and technological dimension, these processes have to be accountable for new value systems:

1. A private sector worldwide has shown that unless the person who consumes the outcomes of the product or the process is involved in those activities from the beginning, many products and solutions don't produce any impact and find that they are wasteful investments. This is as clear in public development as it is in the private sector and therefore new paradigms of engaging communities of practice are required. The solution beneficiaries must be involved in the process right from the beginning.

2. Increasingly development investments have been guided by professional Northern technology driven and seemingly exclusive institutions that see the upper income markets in the global South as their primary market as the Northern population shrinks. It is the responsibility and the contribution of both elites in the North and the South to recognise the volume of impoverishment and vulnerability that exists today and that is going to grow exponentially in the next two decades as extreme weather events destroy survival habitats. Those are communities with whom new practices, new strategies, new products, and new systems have to be developed.

3. Having witnessed many discussions set up by the Secretariat representatives of the New Bauhaus for industry leaders, there is absolutely no awareness, no knowledge and no sensitivity about the needs of those who are not in the top 35% of income brackets either in the North or the South. This is both dangerous and undermines everybody's commitment to social justice.

4. The New Bauhaus has a strong responsibility to make investments that can proudly acknowledge that these funded processes are set to produce a more equitable world that impacts beyond Europe. Explorations can be made in collaboration with activists deeply committed to issues of equity and qualitative impact-focused strategies in the Global South. Results can impact political and technology leaders in the South who copy what is being done in the North by drawing attention to the development deficits and the climate-linked devastation that we have to prepare for.

A Mission for cultural and societal sustainability tailored to each region

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In formulating a response to this working paper, we would like to: a) highlight some elements of the New European Bauhaus vision that are not yet fully crystallised in this document; b) to address a perceived tension in this document, where on the one hand it claims that the new Mission will ‘place inhabitants at the heart of the transformation’, while on the other, the competitiveness and transformation of the construction industry and built environment take centre stage.

Europe finds itself confronted with a multitude of challenges, accompanied by a burgeoning collective awareness of the depleting state of our planet's finite resources. These realities urgently demand upgrades in actions to expedite a comprehensive transformation. Climate change, the most pressing crisis of our time, cannot be attributed solely to natural forces; it predominantly arises from human activities. In our pursuit of addressing ecological imperatives, we must also design environments that incorporate considerations of cultural and societal sustainability, attained through collaboration across disciplines. The New European Bauhaus emerged as a platform characterised by a holistic mission, offering an encouraging framework for our collective endeavours.

European nations grapple with a litany of issues, including the ominous spectre of extreme climate events, escalating temperatures, the emergence of heat islands, desertification, and prolonged droughts. Simultaneously, they share a rich tapestry of history and diverse cultural heritage that merits safeguarding as they confront these climatic emergencies.

Close collaboration, research and co-design among European nations hold the potential to fortify their collective resilience in the face of shared threats, fostering the development of social and nature-based solutions that are both sustainable and accessible. These solutions must be affordable, inclusive, and imbued with aesthetic sensibilities, aligning harmoniously with the vision articulated by the New European Bauhaus. Aligning shared endeavours in a consolidated mission fosters the operationalisation of these goals.

Environmental challenges, resource utilisation, and inclusive societal solutions necessitate bespoke responses tailored to each region. Adapting policies and actions to congruent climates, ecosystems, cultures, and societal issues, have already been the subject of region-specific platforms, such as NEB of the Mountains, NEB on the Danube, NEB Goes South, Nordic Carbon Neutral NEB, NEB Bauhaus of the Seas Sails, and others.

A Mission that embeds passive strategies and the value of traditional knowledge

- Recent crises have highlighted the need for coordinated collaboration.
- “No-tech” should include recognition of passive strategies and value of traditional knowledge embedded in traditional skills and techniques. It should be defined as “natural resources and utilisation of passive strategies”.

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- In addition to building on the European Wood Policy Platform (woodPoP), the Mission can build on other [re]usable and location-specific bio-based materials such as straw/hay, sheep's wool, natural hemp, seaweed, sea shells, etc.
- Instead of stating that we will probably first overshoot, and then work our way back, we should contrast active measures (solar panels, heat recovery systems and technical performance components) with passive measures (orientation, topography, breathable, natural and slow energy exchange materials), when designing or reusing built structure. The ultimate passive measure would be when choosing not to intervene with structure at all (no new building). When working with historic structures and contact zones between old and new, the conservative (conservationist) approach is already accepted, preferring minimal interventions or reversible solutions with a minimal intrusion/alteration. It is important to stress that in parallel to climate change, there is a strong need to reduce waste and wasteful practices which encroach nature, increase pollution and negatively impact on human and animal health and wellbeing.
- “Not leaving anyone behind” will require a location and site specific knowledge and application which takes cognisance of Europe's eight micro-climatic zones and their specificities which are manifested in the traditional knowledge and skills often in evidence in historic building ensembles and infrastructure(s).
- In terms of the General Objective, it is an imperative to put the public interest, people and nature back at the centre of policies and decision-making processes that affect our living environment (see 1 The Architects Council of Europe. Manifesto on the New European Bauhaus. DRAFT Paper for Adoption, October 2023). This will empower and refocus the local authorities to seek and create adequate platforms for citizens' engagement and inclusion in the decision making processes.
- Specific Objective 1: Make Europe's construction ecosystem the world leader in circular and regenerative approaches, delivering key knowledge, technologies, skills, inclusive business models, and jobs for a fair green transition and EU's strategic autonomy with an emphasis on cross-sectoral and cross-disciplinary collaboration.
- The 6th mission will clearly articulate and address the gaps between administrative, technical (environmental) and cultural (societal) space and help mobilise the stakeholders across different sectors and disciplines to engage with a clear common focus. This would enable the participation and applicability of circular economy as an overarching ethos and commitment right down to the practices and methods in the construction sector, maintenance of built structures, demolition and reuse of building material, waste management
- Outcomes under Specific Objective 1: Mapping of the re-use and salvage centres; mapping of the construction demolition waste points and categories; effective and timely waste management for re-use; mapping of secondary and tertiary reuse potential for construction waste; mapping of waste collection hazards and

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prevention; Digitalisation of construction waste management along the supply chain; Reduction in demolition (structures and materials) Defining the Re-use guidelines using knowledge from the heritage sector; (Re)defining the role of urban planners, architects, conservation architects, landscape architects, interior architects, designers and artists to embed the circular economy principles in the briefing and design process.

- Research areas under Specific Objective 2: Identify, evaluate and clarify the stages and stakeholders in development process in built environment; Elaborate cradle-to-cradle from micro to macro-level; Map and elaborate governance process from micro (local authority) to macro-level (department, ministry) concerning development process in the built environment, to include inception, feasibility, implementation, follow up, evaluation, maintenance and new briefs.
- Outcomes under Specific Objective 3: Map the system/good practices / challenges / obstacles to allow for an inclusive R&I and investment; Identify gaps and recommend improvements and pilot solutions

- A Mission that supports a long-term shift towards regenerative practice and understands the primary importance of dynamic and entangled relationships

Regenerative approaches and processes are increasingly acknowledged for their importance in creating changes that respect the planetary boundaries. In the working paper, this approach is mentioned within Objective 1 – Make Europe’s construction ecosystem the world leader in circular and regenerative approaches. In Desire, we have experimented with regenerative processes in relation to citizens' involvement and a holistic understanding of transformation of a place, applying regenerative design processes at one of our territorial sites with the aim of letting decisions emerge from carefully listening to the place we inhabit. The outcome has been successful but also with strong points for reflection, especially that regenerative design processes require time.

Based on this, a clear overall recommendation for the NEB Mission is to *allow for lengthy and open processes without estimated outcomes but with curiosity towards what emerges*. Jenny Andersson from the Really Regenerative Centre (partner in Desire) outlines in this article from a personal point of view how Donella Meadow’s interventions for human behaviour can inspire how we work with transformation in Desire (and beyond) and which questions we may find relevant to pose: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/news/desire-and-dancing-with-systems> - some background information about the territorial site referred to can be found through this link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/sites/kalundborg-circular-campus-kalundborg-denmark>

Challenge 2: Accelerating climate change and the pace of transformation needs to follow

- **Objective 1: Make Europe’s construction ecosystem the world leader in circular and regenerative approaches**
- **Objective 3: Boost public and private investment in R&I, support innovative funding practices and finance new business models**

“Our understanding of value should recognise the primary importance of dynamic and entangled relationships rather than being founded on notions of assets and ownership.” This quote stems from ‘Designing Our Futures: A New European Bauhaus Economy’, an invitation paper developed as part of Desire and aiming at a paradigm shift in how we understand and perceive value. The invitation paper can be found through the following link – the invitation paper will be followed by a White Paper which is expected ready by the spring 2024: https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/assets/uploads/20230707-New-European-Bauhaus-Economy_Digital-version_DML.pdf

The ideas outlined in this invitation paper and further elaborated in the coming White Paper present a fundamentally different perspective on what is needed for transformation at speed and scale. The aim is to support the shift towards a regenerative future for our built

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environment, and therefore, this paper encompasses more of the challenges and objectives set with the NEB Mission working paper. The recommendation for the NEB Mission can therefore be described as *the need to work with a regenerative understanding of value and to unfold and investigate this notion further through activities that point to concrete and context-based learnings*.

It touches upon a vast array of perspectives: new standards and typologies, material innovation, circularity capacity, adaptive reuse and sharing, new finance infrastructures and redefinition of growth, etc. Each of these and their application in combination calls for further research and investigation, experimentation and exploration within contexts of different scope and scale.

Challenge 3: Deepening existing social and territorial inequalities and risk of eroding trust in democratic institutions

- **Objective 2: People-centred governance of transformation processes**

Transdisciplinary, participatory processes can enable local empowerment by engaging neighbourhoods and bring innovative solutions. Digital solutions ease the interaction between the public and the local authorities by bringing anonymized data that represent sentiments at neighbourhood level – data that can be used further for dialogues between different stakeholder groups.

In Desire, one of our experiments has proved that by using a design framework like the one used by architects in their daily business, in activities that engage groups of citizens with no prior experience with or knowledge of design processes, we see local empowerment, systemic understanding of territorial transformation but also innovative ideas and solutions that bring added values for the involved businesses. The key element here is the interaction between professionals and non-professionals on an equal level where the engagement is based on a mutual perception of the qualities that both types of stakeholders bring to the table. The learnings and outputs are described in this article: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/news/gxn-design-is-not-about-hocus-pocus>

The recommendation for the NEB Mission is to *open for further investigation into the interaction between professionals and non-professionals within transformations in the built environment*. To provide research-based knowledge on potential benefits – economically, socially, environmentally, culturally – but also to analyse impact on a longer term: Do we create better solutions by working in transdisciplinary, participatory processes; what do we mean by ‘better solutions’, and how do we measure what is better and for whom?

This may fit well with the neighbourhood scale that is emphasised in the working paper. Still a recommendation here may be to consider involving the policy level as well – we risk losing the benefit of local empowerment if the ideas and solutions being brought forward run aground on legislative barriers or inadequate political interest or will to implement them. *The NEB Mission should also include multilevel involvement and engagement* to ensure long-term

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implementation of proposed solutions and the support and acknowledgement of the legitimacy of local engagement processes.

In this context, the exploration of *digital data and digital tools as means to create involvement and maintain the interest and engagement of citizens* and local stakeholders should be integrated as a key point of interest in the NEB Mission. In Desire, we apply a digital tool, Our Walk App, to support citizens' involvement at different sites. It provides unique data but also a starting point for dialogues that support the interest and further engagement. An article describing the use of Our Walk App is available through this link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/news/app-helps-collect-soft-data-in-the-city>

Finally, art as a language that opens to new understandings has the potential of changing our perceptions of places and neighbourhoods. Art used deliberately to create dialogues with local citizens supports a sensitivity to the places we inhabit and creates a sense of belonging and agency that is necessary in our transformation processes. When art is the spoken language, we become open to acknowledging unknown and unseen aspects of our neighbourhoods, to recognizing the existence of other species and their importance seen from a biodiversity perspective.

In Desire, art is the key ingredient in activities taking place at one of our territorial sites. The Garden Caretaker is a concept that reinterprets the caretaker role we know so well into a new role with artists listening to a place, to what was before and what is and the different forms of life and artefacts characterising that place: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/sites/herlev-asfalt-fabrik-herlev-denmark>

As a movement founded in a perception of the importance of culture to engage and deliver a green transition, the NEB Mission should take *art seriously as a language that opens for new understandings and dialogues*. The role of art as a transformative discipline should be investigated and tested further in new and different contexts, with specific reference to citizens' engagement and people-centred governance.

An entangled, messy, beautiful Mission that is a moonshot like no other

The NEB's broad and diverse adoption across countries, regions, communities in just three years is testament to its value and worth. Since its inception, its strength lies in its rigorous approach to inclusivity – inviting *all* citizens to contribute to its foundation and development. This insistence on co-design and its decentralised network structure – as a means to collaborate on multi-valent solutions to the climate crisis – is novel and precious.

In 2023 over 1400 participants entered the NEB Awards. Transdisciplinary actions, involving over 600 NEB Partners, more than 80 NEB Friends, with reach and impact in all member

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states, through research, innovation and on-the-ground practice demonstrate the value of a multi-valent approach in addressing the complex, entangled, material, social and ethical challenge of rapid anthropogenic climate change. Instead of “either-or”, a ‘both-and’ approach is needed, that brings together agents and actors from places of all scales, from academia, industry, creative practice, policy. Top down *and* bottom up. Qualitative *and* quantitative.

To date, the NEB as a movement has resisted any hierarchical drive to find single solutions and instead welcomes complexity, risk, mess, plurality of perspectives, allowing in multiple voices and experience to negotiate and co-create resilient pathways that are regenerative by design and in action. The contributions to this paper demonstrate the commitment to resist single reduced positions.

The recent energy crisis in the EU, as an unforeseen outcome of the invasion of Ukraine demonstrated the brittle-ness and lack of resilience of single dependencies and safe assumptions. They can have similarly unforeseen negative ethical, material, social, cultural and natural impacts. Thus a plural, fundamentally democratic, radically inclusive mission is more likely to generate resilient, collaborative, place-specific but scalable and replicable solutions that can be rapidly shared and adopted.

The core question remains: how can we transform from an extractive economy to a regenerative society? Despite recent advances we are still extracting more resources from the planet than we replenish, further extending beyond the planetary boundaries which the planet can sustain. To become circular, we need to replenish at scale, in everything we do, across behaviours, economies, society, politics. In what we eat, what we wear, how we use land, in how we provide for the shelter and the health and well-being of citizens and neighbours.

A dedicated NEB Mission asks us to imagine what this might look and feel like, and how to achieve it. This is a moonshot like no other. It will require all our best minds, our creative intelligence, bolstered by our cultural heritage, local knowledge and skill, as well as tenacity that holds to values of equity in the face of breakdown of social cohesion. This is perhaps our best chance to not only meet the targets of the EU Green Deal, but to design and co-create a better Europe in the process.

A programme that creates a Strategic Blueprint for Sustainable Construction

I. Digitalisation as the key transformation of AECO sector –Architecture Engineering Construction Operation

Value Innovation Platform for Construction 4.0

Types of actions:

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Reforms aimed at structural changes, investment in human capital, investment in material capital -such as infrastructures-, investment in intangible capital -such as software, R+D+i, and/or investment in natural capital

One sector that did not industrialise its processes is that of **Construction**, in need of a more important transformation than the other sectors since it is the **most lagging behind in its digitalization**, the one with the **lowest productivity**, the one with the **highest accident rate** and **is not sustainable** in itself.

Therefore, it requires the introduction of this paradigm shift in all the areas that comprise it: starting with the transformation of those who will be its future workers -either from the training field, both from Secondary Education and Vocational Training and in the university and professional environment and with the "push" that will generate a viralisation produced by a television series on the impact of digital on the built-, to the components of its business fabric -both technically and professionally-, through its processes.

It is the implementation of **digitization throughout its value chain**, from the production of raw materials to rehabilitation and deconstruction, adapting software, hardware and workflows to be used in a common and collaborative way by all its agents. It is the only way in this sector to reach **Circular Construction**.

It is needed that a part of resources is allocated to the **conversion and updating** of the laws on which the contracting of works and projects is based, introducing the mandatory use of digitization methodologies for sustainable and competitive industrialization based on digital models (BIM), their programming (Lean), the responsibility of attributions (IPD) and their financing.

II. Objectives

Assessment of the impacts on the economy and future employment

With the actions of DigiNEB Construction 4.0 program, the impact on the economy and employment in 5 years will be divided into two axes: the adaptation of existing companies and the creation of new companies.

The proposal foresees the generation of an **increase in GDP in the construction sector and increase in the number of employees**.

The **industrialization of Construction 4.0** contemplates all the stages of the life cycle of a construction -be it building or infrastructure-, from the extraction of materials to create the primary products to the set that allows to "manufacture" a building in a closed, heated, controlled warehouse... understanding that this assembled set can be taken to work and allow its export.

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The Construction 4.0 program contemplates from the generation of resources to the **introduction of process change**, attending to the actions of designing, ordering and programming in order to be efficient in all processes for the transformation of a built. A **built asset that will halve its production time, its cost, its placing on the market and its polluting emissions**.

III. Consideration of DigiNEB Tractor Macroproject

1. **Europe vision.** *Have a vision of the continent, in the form of transversality and positive impact on other sectors and on the economy as a whole.*
2. **European Semester.** *Respond to the challenges identified by the European Commission, both in the business fabric and in society, so that, if achieved, a leading position can be achieved at a global level, with a focus on employment.*
3. **Double ecological and digital transition.** *Contribute to economic recovery and growth, job creation, the transformation of the productive model in ecological and/or digital terms, the improvement of productivity and social and territorial structuring, mitigating the socioeconomic impact of the crisis and reinforcing cohesion and convergence. All this taking advantage of the opportunities offered by technological advances and innovation processes.*
4. **Leadership.** *Focus on those areas or sectors in which a relevant competitive advantage can be achieved at a global level. In the current international context, uncertain and changing, these projects could also serve to maintain the leading position occupied by our continent in certain areas.*
5. **Reindustrialization.** *Promote the resilience of the European economy, through the creation of new value chains in industry or, where appropriate, improve and modernize existing ones.*
6. **Public-private collaboration.** *Assume the leadership of the projects by the private sector, with the involvement of the affected sectors, but with the firm and determined support of the Administration, so that it finally becomes an exportable project through the EU brand.*
7. **Traction.** *Generate or strengthen collaborative ecosystems involving large, medium and small companies; together with the support of the different public administrations and, if possible, universities and technology centres.*
8. **Scalability.** *Have a rapid scalability that allows an early profit of the actions proposed and a complete execution within the deadlines set by the European Commission.*

9. **Milestones and partial goals.** *Have a focus on continuous improvement through cycles of maturity, with tangible partial achievements from early stages. The achievements of these projects should facilitate significant advances in the competitiveness of the sectors targeting the solutions.*

10. **Continent potential.** *Take advantage of the differential advantages of each country, among which are existing or planned infrastructures, social and cultural characteristics or geographical nature itself, among others.*

Construction as a global entity (it would be better to call it the AECO-F sector, Architecture-Engineering-Construction-Operator and Manufacturer) implies between 8 and 20% of the GDP of any country in the world.

It involves a long list of agents: Public and private developers, urban planners and planners, geographers, cartographers, geologists, topographers, architects and technical architects, industrial, road, civil engineers, public works, builders, contractors, manufacturers, suppliers, installers, all kinds of guilds -painters, plasterers, welders, carpenters...-, maintainers, energy, acoustic, sustainability consultants, project managers, facility managers, and a long etcetera that includes its training entities (vocational training centres and universities), governance (professional associations, associations and guilds). We are talking about changing an entire sector and this automatically becomes a macro-project.

It has been shown that the construction sector is the one that generates more jobs for fewer euros invested and therefore, is the best and safest bet.

Why the Construction 4.0 Strategic Plan for the transformation of the construction sector, is it really a macro-project tractor?

1. Country vision

For its **weight in the country's economy** (8-20% of GDP).

1bis. For its implementation throughout the **territory** and in all the autonomous communities.

1 tris. This is a project based on collaborative resilience without borders between professions, between transnational and trans-sectorial sectors: from agroforestry – the cycle from the very seed of a tree that in 10 years will become raw material of a technological CLT-cross laminated timber wooden structure to the transformation and reuse of manufactured spaces, or the design of a real estate development, through the digitization of three-dimensional models of infrastructures and buildings that make up a city, its activity and its territory.

2. European Semester

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The project directly addresses the following challenges of the European Semester:

- i. Delay in the governance structure for public procurement
- ii. Limited success in reducing the use of temporary contracts.
- iii. Introduction of new strategies for the education and training of professionals to alleviate technical skills in the labour market.
- iv. Limited progress in fostering innovation and energy efficiency.
- v. Decrease in labour productivity compared to other continents.
- vi. Innovation below the EU average.
- vii. Low quality employment and qualification.
- viii. A small number of specialists in information and communication technologies.
- ix. Accelerate the transition to decarbonising energy consumption and increasing energy efficiency at the level of buildings and districts.
- x. Territorial cohesion by introducing industrialised productive capacity in rural and peripheral areas.
- xi. Low affordability of housing.
- xii. Valorisation of vocational training, expansion of the range of courses, cooperation with companies and promotion of online.
- xiii. The low use of new technologies by SMEs.
- xiv. Reactivation of the economy, where the construction sector is one of the sectors where the greatest impact can be generated for every euro invested.
- xv. Focus on the European Green Deal on climate neutrality.
- xvi. Work towards a sector based on digital and non-manual technology, improving supply chains.

3. Double ecological and digital transition

The **number of agents** involved in the value chain of this project and the need to harmonise the project within a collaborative environment to make it effective guarantees the approach to this double mission.

The approach is precisely to improve productivity and competitiveness thanks to its digitalization and sustainability.

Because it is the **sector that produces the most damage to the environment** (waste production, zero recyclability, maximum emissions, outdated processes, huge energy

consumption, etc.) and needs energy efficiency, decarbonisation of its activity, and a better use of resources.

The project aims to emulate innovative policies of industrial leadership 4.0 and digitalization of benchmark countries such as Finland, United Kingdom, France, Germany and Estonia within the construction sector and innovative production processes that have proven their effectiveness.

The Construction 4.0 project aims to contribute to the generation of new economies by helping to create better housing, better access to housing, with the possibility of recovering materials, and not only generating more resources but also guaranteeing the resources of the future. The digitalization of the sector will help to retrain the group of professionals and technicians involved, creating an environment of greater ease to maintain jobs and guaranteeing their future.

On the creation of new jobs and employment, the creation of new professional profiles, the rehabilitation of current professionals, guaranteeing the inclusion of young people and women is assured.

The transformation of the production model in ecological and/or digital terms is based on four axes: the introduction of wood as a sustainable building material, the introduction of the circular construction criterion, the introduction of DfMA or design for assembly and dismantling, and the introduction of the concept of digital twin for the management of the built environment.

Improving productivity in the construction sector is very easy: construction has a negative productivity dragged down over the last 60 years and at the same time we want to reduce the accident rate on site by removing people from the work by putting them to work in a more controlled space, better climatologically speaking, improving working conditions in a warehouse, however, taking advantage of the opportunities offered by technological advances and BIM, LEAN, IPD and Digital Twin innovation processes, bases of industrialised construction.

4. Leadership

Among the participating entities there is a representative of SMEs, a provider of knowledge and disseminator of acquired and promoted knowledge, a set of backbone entities, and more than one with sufficient organisational technical capacity to carry out the R+D+I activities that the tractor project incorporates.

The aim is to lead the sector to become a new construction export factor.

In the current VUCA international context, uncertain and changing, this project must serve to maintain construction in its leading position that it occupies in our continent.

5. Reindustrialization

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Talking about reindustrializing the construction sector is difficult because it can be considered that it is not yet an industrialised sector. Boosting the resilience of the European economy in the field of construction involves first industrialising the sector. It is not a situation specific to Europe since the lack of productivity in the construction sector is something that affects all continents in a general way. Before that, it is time to take the sector to what is called Industrialised Construction, a concept that is achieved through the creation of new value chains in the industry and improving and modernizing existing ones.

The composition of the sector is mainly **99.1% of SMEs** and the SME sector is the target of this action.

6. Public-private partnerships

The creation of a consortium of several entities and companies of all kinds is an example of a transparent and broad collaboration of what can be considered the public-private spectrum of this sector.

The Construction 4.0 Project involves all affected sectors in a plural project, breaking the silos in which the information and communication of each participating agent is found.

7. Traction

The working group, under the form of a DigiNEB consortium, is in itself a collaborative ecosystem and an example of the continent's productive panorama.

Large companies with turnover of nearly 2,000 million euros a year to small companies with turnover of 100,000 euros are involved; there are professional associations with more than 100,000 members and there are corporations of less than a hundred; represents all professions in the sector; it is the representative of the municipalities of EU at the same time that regional technology centres appear; and we have universities and faculties of Architecture, Engineering, Economics and Law and also vocational training centres with studies of the Construction range.

The traction that this project will provide is total, it has full **capacity for real sectoral transformation** and therefore should guarantee and multiply the employability effect.

8. Scalability

Because its effects are **medium and long term**, we are talking about the restructuring of an entire sector where the effects should not only be scalable but replicable.

The project contemplates rapid scalability by creating replicability centres in different provinces. This will allow an early benefit from the actions proposed as the improvement of the quality of all the assets built. But at a smaller level, the lower grain would be, for example, the profits generated by winning competitions in other countries, the reduction of consumption bills thanks to energy savings, the improvement of

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management through digital twins – reduction of pollution, mobility, energy poverty, social, economic and environmental sustainability-...

9. Milestones and partial goals

The strategic project uses the Lean Construction methodology based on TPS to agree actions and objectives with weekly feedback when introducing Kaizen processes of continuous improvement, allowing an Agile pivoting in order to obtain what in the Anglo-Saxon world is known as "low hanging fruits".

The action plan also has monitoring KPIs as monitoring indicators also in order to guarantee the achievements of the project. In fact, each of them must translate into a double-digit advance in the competitiveness of each link in the chain of agents involved. This project only pursues the impact, change and real trans-training of the AECO sector layers a new situation that gives it a future.

The participation of the only segment of the value chain that is industrialized, that of manufacturers of materials, products and construction systems is fundamental in order to take their R+D+i to the entire life cycle of a construction project.

Construction companies must become assemblers, assemblers and technicians in execution processes that guarantee the design processes that architects and engineers conceive.

Digitalization and its implementation must mean a **paradigm shift** as it has been in all other sectors – and that in the architecture, engineering and construction sector has not been accepted or adopted naturally.

10. Continent potential

The benefits of the Construction 4.0 project are not only limited to the companies that participate but also have a social and economic relevance. The project aims to lay the foundations for sustainable growth – integrating economic, environmental and social vectors – in order to give durability to the project. The economic benefits are clear by attributing greater competitiveness to all companies, its effects on public housing, communication infrastructures and city management will be multiplied and the environmental effects will be reflected in the control and minimization of emissions, the improvement of energy management and the use of water and materials.

As a reference from other countries in a similar situation, we find dozens of documents promoting an action similar to the one that this project promotes. It is worth mentioning the latest report by Mark Farmer, entitled "Modernise or die" <https://www.constructionleadershipcouncil.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/Farmer-Review.pdf> and with a no less enlightening subtitle:

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Time to decide the industry's future. The macro-project must be the decision in time to face this challenge.

Professionally, the continent has a long tradition in design architecture, quality manufacturing, vision without borders... And this forms a scenario that allows this turning point.

The project wants to resume the scenario in which the continent was valued as a world reference in design and architecture, now it will have to be in construction and manufacturing, introducing in its methodology the concepts of modular construction, offsite, cradle-to-cradle, industrialised construction, and circular construction.

[1] <https://e-publishing.cern.ch/index.php/CIJ/>

[2] https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/eu-valorisation-policy/knowledge-valorisation-platform/thematic-focus/communities-practice-complete-their-work-co-create-codes-practice-industry-academia-collaboration_en

[3] <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32023H0499&qid=1678171231088>

[4] https://www.ami2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/2022-12-09_Materials_2030_RoadMap_VF4.pdf

[5] <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/oa-edit/10.1201/9781003337966-5/internet-things-applications-future-manufacturing-john-soldatos-sergio-gusmeroli-pedro-malo-giovanni-di-orio>

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